

Compendium on data standards for interoperability in DRR and CCA

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Executive summary

This compendium is a strategic effort to define a **structured set of data standards**, promoting interoperability within the realms of Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA). We aim to craft a cohesive framework that ensures the seamless interchange of data across a diverse array of models, databases and both analytical and visualization tools, with the ultimate goal to enhancing the efficacy of DRR and CCA initiatives.

Additionally, the assessment focuses on standards that facilitate the **closure of prevalent gaps** in spatio-temporal scales and enable comprehensive multi-hazard and multi-risk assessments.

Proposed methodology grounds in the principles and recommendations of the European Interoperability Framework (EIF) and aligns with the strategic directives set forth in the EU eGovernment Action Plan 2016–2020. It involves a thorough analysis of interoperable standards endorsed by renowned international entities, such as the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), and aligns with established EU initiatives, notably INSPIRE.

In the evaluative process, particular attention has been paid to replicability of successful existing practices exemplified by initiatives like The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) Preview, Copernicus, and others. A rigorous Multi-Criteria Assessment, informed by the FAIR principles is employed to rank these standards. The intent is to **distill a compendium of interoperability best practices** that are not only reusable but are also optimally suited for DRR and CCA applications. Moreover, this compendium explores the crucial mechanisms of **collaboration and stakeholder engagement**, recognizing the importance of multi-stakeholder analysis in enhancing interoperability and ensuring that data tools are shaped by, and responsive to, the needs of a broad spectrum of actors in the DRR and CCA domains.

The outcomes of this compendium are poised to inform the architectural design and technical specifications of the **Data Fabric** component also developed in DIRECTED. Furthermore, the analysis provides a foundational baseline for determining the Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) of various interoperable tools, setting the stage for their subsequent development and integration.

Critical to the success of interoperability in DRR and CCA is the establishment of **standardized taxonomies and ontologies**, as explored for example by the Climate Connectivity Hub¹, developed by SEI. Such standardization lays the foundation for clear data interaction and semantic interoperability, which are instrumental in informed decision-making processes.

The **overarching ambition** of this compendium is to serve as a cornerstone for building a more resilient, responsive, and integrated DRR and CCA data ecosystem, empowering stakeholders to make informed decisions in the face of growing climate-related challenges.

¹ e.g. a search on 'flood' in the Climate Connectivity Hub: <https://connectivity-hub.weadapt.org/?resource=https%3A%2F%2Fapi-uat.connectivity-hub.com%2Fapi%2Fkeyword%2F58d1c857-2638-477d-bc96-ce5b3afc0ee0.jsonld>

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List of Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
API	APPLICATION PROGRAMMING INTERFACE
CDS	CLIMATE DATA STORE
CCA	CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION
CLMS	COPERNICUS LAND MONITORING SERVICE
COG	CLOUD OPTIMIZED GEOTIFF
CSV	COMMA SEPARATED VALUES
CSW	CATALOGUE SERVICE FOR THE WEB
DEM	DIGITAL ELEVATION MODEL
DRM	DISASTER RISK MANAGEMENT
DRR	DISASTER RISK REDUCTION
EDR	ENVIRONMENTAL DATA RETRIEVAL
EIF	EUROPEAN INTEROPERABILITY FRAMEWORK
FAIR	FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE AND REUSABLE
GEOJSON	GEOSPATIAL JAVASCRIPT OBJECT NOTATION
GML	GEOGRAPHY MARKUP LANGUAGE
GPX	GPS EXCHANGE FORMAT
HDF	HIERARCHICAL DATA FORMAT
ICT	INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY
INSPIRE	INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SPATIAL INFORMATION IN THE EUROPEAN COMMUNITY
IPCC	INTERGOVERNMENTAL PANEL ON CLIMATE CHANGE
KML	KEYHOLE MARKUP LANGUAGE
LAS	LIDAR DATA EXCHANGE FORMAT
MCA	MULTI-CRITERIA ASSESSMENT
NETCDF	NETWORK COMMON DATA FORM
OGC	OPEN GEOSPATIAL CONSORTIUM
RWL	REAL WORLD LAB
SDGs	SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS
STAC	SPATIOTEMPORAL ASSET CATALOG
TIFF	TAGGED IMAGE FILE FORMAT
TMS	TILE MAP SERVICE
WCS	WEB COVERAGE SERVICE
WFS	WEB FEATURE SERVICES
WMS	WEB MAP SERVICE
WMTS	WEB MAP TILE SERVICE
WKT	WELL-KNOWN TEXT
XML	EXTENSIBLE MARKUP LANGUAGE

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and context

In the unfolding era of climate urgency, Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) are becoming increasingly **interlinked**. The increasing frequency of extreme weather events due to climate change calls for a unified strategy to mitigate disaster impacts. Recognizing this, a **guide on data standards** for enhancing cooperation between DRR and CCA has been developed to tackle the **complexities** at the intersection of environmental change and societal resilience. Historically, DRR has focused on **preempting** disasters through risk understanding and strategic planning, evolving to incorporate strategies from infrastructural resilience to community-based early warnings. Climate change, introducing new risk variables, necessitates an expanded approach. CCA complements this by aiming to strengthen the resilience of communities, systems, and infrastructures against long-term climate shifts.

The **recent natural disasters** in Germany in 2021 (Thieken et al., 2022) and Italy's Emilia-Romagna Region in May 2023² have underscored climate change as a risk multiplier, emphasizing the need for integrated DRR and CCA efforts. However, achieving effective collaboration and interoperability between the **myriad of stakeholders**, from international bodies to local communities, presents a significant challenge. This challenge is compounded by the diverse and often incompatible data standards, models, and tools used in risk assessment and mitigation.

Interoperability—the ability for different systems and organizations to work together seamlessly—is vital for enhancing disaster and climate change resilience (Migliorini et al., 2019). Yet, **barriers** such as incompatible data standards and the “**siloed**” nature of data repositories have hindered its potential. Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort to promote data sharing and develop common frameworks, such as those proposed by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) and the FAIR data principles. Effective **stakeholder collaboration**, underpinned by shared goals and common standards, is essential for overcoming these barriers. **Governance** reforms that define clear roles, responsibilities, and data management processes are crucial for fostering an ecosystem where data can flow freely between stakeholders. This not only enhances interoperability but also leads to more informed and effective responses to the pressing challenges of disaster risk and climate change.

² <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2023/may/17/italy-storms-people-dead-thousands-evacuated-emilia-romagna>

1.2 Objectives and scope

This compendium aims to a **unified set** of data standards, protocols, and practices to improve information exchange among different systems and stakeholders in DRR and CCA. Its goals are practical and forward-looking, aiming to meet current interoperability needs while building a resilient infrastructure that can adapt to the fast pace of climate change and technological development. This compendium strives to **overcome barriers** by enabling communication across different systems with common data standards. It uses digital technology to identify patterns and connections at various levels and encourages a multidisciplinary approach by merging data from different fields. The main objective is to facilitate the **integration** of varied data sources—like satellite images, sensor networks, climate models, and local records—into a unified, **actionable knowledge** base. This is crucial for crafting accurate risk assessments, devising effective response strategies, and efficiently allocating resources for disaster management. The **harmonization** of data standards is essential for realizing the full benefits of these integrated approaches, underlining the practical importance of interoperability.

At its heart, the compendium addresses the issue of data **heterogeneity**—diverse formats, standards, and meanings that separate disaster risk and climate adaptation data. By proposing standardized methods, it seeks to close the communication **gaps** that often block cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral cooperation. It aims to create a shared language and protocols that allow different systems to interact, boosting our collective ability to predict, comprehend, and lessen disaster impacts. This document is more than a technical guide; it's a **blueprint for future resilience**, aligning with global initiatives like the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, the European Union's Civil Protection Mechanism, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly those focused on sustainable communities, information access, and partnership cultivation. The compendium covers a **broad range of DRR and CCA activities**, from early warnings and emergency responses to long-term recovery and mitigation. It addresses the needs at both local and international levels, emphasizing the significance of not just technical but also semantic interoperability—making sure data is exchangeable and understandable across various contexts and cultures.

It also leverages **recent advances** in geospatial technology, cloud computing, and big data analytics, highlighting the importance of standards that support the real-time processing and visualization of vast datasets essential for responding to evolving disaster scenarios.

Moreover, the compendium supports the implementation of major **international agreements** like the Sendai Framework, the Paris Agreement, and the SDGs. It serves as a practical reference for governments, NGOs, researchers, and businesses to align their DRR and CCA initiatives with these global commitments. Recognizing the evolving nature of DRR and CCA, the compendium is designed to be **adaptable**, incorporating emerging technologies and methods. It includes a process for regular review and updates to keep the standards current and effective.

In summary, this compendium **guides stakeholders through the complexities** of DRR and CCA data management, addressing both current and future interoperability needs. It emphasizes the integration of DRR and CCA through interoperable data standards as a crucial step towards building a more resilient and adaptive society.

1.3 Overview of the methods and approach

The methodology behind this compendium is **detailed and iterative**, aimed at establishing a comprehensive set of **best practices and standards** amidst the diverse global data systems landscape. This approach includes several **key steps** to build a flexible and robust interoperability framework.

Initially, the methodology involves an extensive **review** of existing data standards and protocols, covering areas from meteorological data to geospatial systems, and including contributions from international and regional bodies. This review identifies the **strengths and weaknesses** of current standards to build on successful models of data interoperability while pinpointing remaining challenges.

Following this review is an **analysis phase** where standards are evaluated based on the FAIR data principles, ensuring they are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. This ensures the chosen standards meet high usability and accessibility criteria.

The next step synthesizes this information into **proposed standards** and practices, balancing technical data interoperability needs with the operational realities of DRR and CCA. A significant focus is on enabling **real-time data exchange** to facilitate swift decision-making in emergencies.

Feedback from stakeholders, gathered through questionnaires in Real World Labs, plays a crucial role in refining these standards to ensure they address user needs effectively. This feedback loop allows for practical testing and iteration of the standards.

Acknowledging the ever-evolving nature of DRR and CCA, the methodology includes provisions for **periodic updates** to the standards, incorporating new technological advancements and changing climate and disaster risk scenarios. This adaptability ensures the long-term relevance and utility of the compendium.

Collaboration is a cornerstone of this methodology, involving an international network of experts, practitioners, and policymakers through workshops, webinars, and other platforms. This collective effort not only broadens the compendium's perspective but also aids in its widespread adoption and implementation.

The end result is a dynamic, **living framework**, not merely a document, designed to support resilient and effective DRR and CCA strategies into the future. By laying out a path towards cohesive interoperability, this methodology aims to **reflect the shared expertise** of the global DRR and CCA communities, establishing a foundation for resilient strategies that evolve with the field's needs.

2. Principles and recommendations for interoperability

2.1 Overview of the European Interoperability Framework

2.1.1 Introduction

In order to facilitate the interactions between the public, businesses and administrations, the European member states have modernized their public administrations by means of digital public services. In the process of digitalizing the public sector, interoperability acts as a key attribute for achieving the digital public services goals. Lack of interoperability may result in limited data flows in the public sector, which in turn can hinder the development of new technologies and increase administrative burdens (Campmas et al., 2022). Administrative silos, lack of coordination and inefficient use of scarce resources are some other challenges that may arise from an absence of interoperability (Misuraca et al., 2020). To tackle these challenges, the **European Interoperability Framework (EIF)** has been developed to offer guidance on how to improve communications between administrations, businesses, and citizens within the European Union and across member state borders. The Framework was first introduced in 2004 and revised twice, in 2010 and 2017.

The EIF defines interoperability as “*the ability of organizations to interact towards mutually beneficial goals, which also includes the sharing of information and knowledge between these organizations, through the business processes they support, by means of the data exchange between their Information and communication technology (ICT) systems*”. The EIF is a commonly agreed procedure for the delivery of European **public services in an interoperable manner**. It consists of three main components: interoperability principles, interoperability layers, and a conceptual model for integrated public services. These components are further accompanied by 47 recommendations, which all public administrations may freely decide to implement.

The interoperability principles offered in the EIF are intended to establish **general behaviors** on interoperability. These principles define the main concepts required for the development of interoperable digital public services. The principles highlight the importance of coordination on interoperability initiatives among the EU member states based on the EIF (the principle of subsidiarity and proportionality). They put focus on key approaches to data and services (transparency, openness, reusability, data portability and technological neutrality). And they emphasize the need to inspire collaboration between public administrations (information preservation, administrative simplification and the continuous assessment of efficiency) and the necessity for considering the needs of the users (user-inclusion and accessibility, security and privacy, centricity, and multilingualism). The underlying principles of the EIF are briefly presented in Section 2.1.2.

The EIF also presents **interoperability layers** which guarantee that national interoperability strategies are aligned with the EIF and, if required, modified or extended to address the national context. Four main interoperability layers and their governance are presented in the framework. *Legal interoperability*, which emphasizes the need for regulatory and legal frameworks for supporting interoperability initiatives. *Organizational interoperability*, which echoes the procedures and guidelines for organizations to facilitate cooperation and data exchanges. *Semantic interoperability*, which emphasizes the capacity of information exchange between systems to be interpreted without ambiguity. And *technical interoperability*, which highlights the necessity for technical infrastructure to enable data exchanges. These layers are briefly explained in Section 2.1.3. Lastly, the EIF also presents a **conceptual model** for integrated public services that aims to support interoperability in European public services. The model underlines the importance of basic components such as open data and base registries (Campmas et al., 2022).

2.1.2 Underlying principles

- **Subsidiarity and proportionality:** The subsidiarity principle calls for decisions made by the EU members to be taken as closely as possible to the citizen. Meaning that the EU should act only when the action is more effective than the same action taken at the national level. The proportionality principle limits EU actions to what is essential to reach the aims of the treaties. The EIF recommends the EU members to align their national interoperability frameworks (NIF) and interoperability strategies with the EIF and, if needed, modify or extend them to the national needs.
- **Openness:** In the context of interoperability of public services, openness is mainly related to data, specifications, and software in the EIF. Open data refers to the concept of public data being freely available for use by others, unless restrictions apply. The EIF recommends data to be published as open source wherever possible, unless certain restrictions apply.
- **Transparency:** is defined in the EIF as allowing other administrations, businesses and citizens to view and understand administrative rules, processes, services, and data. The EIF recommends ensuring the availability of interfaces to internal information systems and securing the right to the protection of personal data.
- **Reusability:** The EIF highly recommends the reuse and sharing of information, data and IT solutions and promotes the use of open-source software unless certain privacy or confidentiality restrictions apply.
- **Technological neutrality and data portability:** It is emphasized to minimize technological dependencies in development of services in order to avoid imposing specific technical implementations or products on citizens, businesses and other administrations. This also highly enables adaptation to the rapidly evolving technological environment.
- **User-centricity:** The EIF recommends the needs of the users to be considered when deciding on the public services to be provided. Their delivery should also be based on a multi-channel delivery approach. It is also recommended for a single point of contact to be offered to the users, in order to hide internal administrative complexity.

- **Inclusion and accessibility:** Inclusion and accessibility should be an essential element in the development life cycle of any European public service in the context of design, information content and delivery. It is recommended that all European public services to be accessible to all citizens, including persons with disabilities, the elderly, and other disadvantaged groups.
- **Security and privacy:** It is essential for the public and businesses to be confident that their interactions with public authorities take place in a secure and trustworthy environment and in compliance with relevant regulations.
- **Multilingualism:** European public services may be used by anyone in any of the Member States. Therefore, the EIF highly recommends multilingualism to be carefully considered in the development of services.
- **Administrative simplification:** The EIF recommends administrative processes to be simplified wherever possible by improving them or eliminating any process that does not provide public value. The digitization of services should consider the concepts of digital-by-default and digital-first. Additionally, digital channels should be used for the delivery of services whenever appropriate.
- **Preservation of information:** Information and records should be stored in electronic form wherever feasible. It should be ensured that records and other forms of information keep their legibility, reliability, and integrity over time and are accessible as long as needed while considering the security and privacy aspects.
- **Assessment of effectiveness and efficiency:** The effectiveness and efficiency of different interoperability solutions and technological options should be continuously assessed, while considering user needs, proportionality, and balance between costs and benefits.

2.1.3 Interoperability layers

- **Legal interoperability:** Legal interoperability highlights the importance of collaboration between organizations operating under different legal frameworks, policies, and strategies. In order to address legal interoperability, existing legislation should be reviewed in order to identify “*interoperability barriers*” such as geographical or sectoral limits in the use and storage of data, over-restrictive requirements to use specific digital technologies, vague data license models, outdated security and data protection regulations, etc.
- **Organizational interoperability:** This type of interoperability mainly relates to how public administrations align their practices, responsibilities, and expectations to accomplish mutually beneficial and commonly agreed goals. Organizational interoperability also emphasizes meeting the needs of the users by making services available, accessible, easily identifiable, and user-focused.
- **Semantic interoperability:** This type of interoperability ensures that the format and meaning of information and data are preserved and understood throughout exchanges between different parties. It is recommended for data and information to be counted as a

public asset which should be appropriately collected, managed, protected, shared, and preserved. The EIF recommends implementation of an information management framework at the highest possible level to avoid fragmentation and duplication.

- **Technical interoperability:** Technical interoperability may consist of different aspects such as: the interconnection between services, interface specifications, data presentation and exchange, data integration services, and secure communication protocols. The EIF recommends the use of open specifications, wherever available, to guarantee technical interoperability in establishing European public services.

In essence, the European Interoperability Framework (EIF) aims to enhance digital public services across EU member states by promoting interoperability. It addresses challenges like administrative silos and inefficient resource use by guiding improvements in communication among administrations, businesses, and citizens. The EIF focuses on interoperability as a means for organizations to share information and knowledge towards mutual goals. It comprises interoperability principles, layers, and a conceptual model, supplemented by recommendations for public administrations. These elements encourage practices like openness, reusability, user-centricity, and multilingualism to develop digital public services that are accessible, efficient, and effective.

2.2 Review of the EU eGovernment Action Plan 2016-2020

2.2.1 Introduction

The EU is continuously increasing efforts to encourage the development and implementation of eGovernment systems (digital tools and innovations functioning as digital public services and technologies) in its member states. eGovernment supports administrative procedures, improves the quality of the services and grows internal public sector efficiency. The new eGovernment action plan was intended to become an integral part of the Digital Single Market (DSM) strategy, which was announced as part of the Digital Agenda for Europe in May 2015 (European Commission, 2016). The European eGovernment Action Plan 2016-2020 focuses on the modernization of public administrations across the EU by the use of eGovernment. In principle, the eGovernment Action Plan serves as a political instrument to promote the modernization of public administrations across the European Union.

The action plan consists of twenty actions with the focus on: modernizing public administration with ICT, using key digital enablers; enabling cross-border mobility with interoperable digital public services and facilitating digital interaction between administrations and citizens and businesses for high-quality public services. Further actions may be proposed either by the Commission or by stakeholders, including member states. The plan also offers seven underlying principles which are briefly presented in Section 2.2.2.

2.2.2 Interoperability layers

- **Digital by Default:** this principle states that digitization should always be the preferred option. Additionally, a single contact point should be offered to the users, for them to avoid the complexity of administrative processes.
- **Once only principle:** This ensures that citizens and businesses supply the same information only once to public administrations.
- **Inclusiveness and accessibility:** This principle emphasizes that digital public services should be designed in a way that are inclusive by default and cater for different needs such as those of the elderly and people with disabilities
- **Openness & transparency:** It is vital that public administrations share data and information between themselves and enable citizens and businesses to access, control and correct their own data.
- **Cross-border by default:** This states that public administrations should make relevant digital public services available across borders and prevent added fragmentation
- **Interoperability by default:** It is important for public services to be developed in a way to work seamlessly across the European single market and across organizational silos, benefiting from the free movement of data and digital services in the EU.
- **Trustworthiness & Security** This states that all initiatives should have compliance with the legal framework on personal data protection, privacy and IT security, by integrating these components in the design phase.

2.3 The Interoperable Europe initiative of the European Commission

The Interoperable Europe initiative of the European Commission³ is centered on enhancing public sector interoperability **across the EU** to promote cross-border cooperation and digital transformation. It supports the development of digital public services that are interconnected and interoperable by design, not just within individual member states but across the entire EU.

A significant aspect of the initiative is the **structured cooperation among public administrations**, which involves both public and private sector stakeholders. These

³<https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/interoperable-europe>

collaborations are guided by a common strategic agenda to facilitate the sharing of data and digital solutions that are secure and can function seamlessly across borders.

The initiative also introduces the Interoperable Europe Act (the EU Council is expected to give its green light on the actually approved text at the end of February 2024⁴) which encompasses several **pillars** designed to foster this environment of cross-border interoperability. These include the establishment of the Interoperable Europe Board, which includes representatives from EU member states and the European Commission, the mandatory assessments for interoperability impacts of IT system changes, and a one-stop-shop platform known as the 'Interoperable Europe Portal' for interoperability solutions and community cooperation.

Additionally, innovation and support measures are a critical part of the initiative, with regulatory sandboxes and GovTech cooperation highlighted as tools for policy experimentation and the scaling up of interoperability solutions for public reuse. The ultimate goal is to deliver **better public services** to citizens and businesses and to support trusted data flows, contributing to the digital targets set for Europe for 2030.

The Interoperable Europe Act aims to foster interoperability in the public sector by establishing a clear legal framework. Key practical measures include:

- Creating the Interoperable Europe Board for strategic planning and monitoring of interoperability initiatives.
- Mandating interoperability assessments for significant IT system changes affecting cross-border services.
- Developing the Interoperable Europe Portal as a one-stop-shop for information and solutions related to interoperability.
- Promoting an open ecosystem for digital technologies in the public sector to ensure transparency and reusability of solutions.

These measures are designed to streamline the collaboration between EU Member States, improve the quality of digital public services, and support the digital single market.

⁴<https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/interoperable-europe/news/european-parliament-adopts-interoperable-europe-act>

2.4 Application of interoperability frameworks in DIRECTED

The DIRECTED project aims specifically at:

- a. Increasing the level of interoperability of existing disaster and risk management tools by improving their data **integration** capacities and combining their outputs in a meaningful way to provide extended functionality for **decision** support.
- b. Informing and supporting an **integrated multi-hazard** DRR and CCA planning in the Real World Laboratories (RWL) and developing innovative solutions.

With regard to these objectives, the underlying principles and recommendations provided by the EIF and the EU eGovernment Action Plan 2016-2020 and the Interoperable Europe initiative of EU Commission may serve as a valuable framework for integrating and promoting interoperability in several areas of the tasks at hand.

The following actions can be recommended for improving the level of interoperability of the existing tools:

- a. Creating a Data Fabric that provides a unified interface for data from the different RWLs and other open source data to be used in the disaster modelling and DRR.
- b. Development of accessible and easy-to-use user interfaces for the tools in order to enhance the user experience while also considering the multilingualism aspect.
- c. Development of online, accessible and comprehensible user manuals and tutorials for the tools.
- d. Combination of the outputs of the models in a meaningful and convenient manner in order to assist and facilitate decision-making.
- e. Making the tools compatible with more file formats, both for input and outputs of the tools (see chapter 4 for suggested formats).
- f. Development of online multilingual websites for the tools.
- g. Offering the tools and also the data used for the tasks as opensource wherever possible and compatible with intellectual property protection.
- h. Publication of the results of the tasks through open-source channels, as well as presentation of the results in international conferences and open-source scientific journals.

Overall, by following the principles and recommendations offered by identified overarching frameworks, interoperability can be significantly promoted in the task for the exchange of data and information for DRR and CCA. It can also be ensured that the resulting standards and best practices are compatible with existing and future public services and eGovernment initiatives.

3. Data encoding and interoperable standards for data exchange

3.1 Introduction and scope of the assessment

The chapter outlines the critical role of interoperable standards, as recognized by the OGC and EU initiatives like INSPIRE, in enhancing geospatial data exchange. Such standards for data exchange play a crucial role in fostering collaboration, promoting data sharing, and ensuring consistency in geospatial information.

Facilitating Interoperability:

OGC Standards: Serve as a universal foundation for geospatial interoperability, allowing diverse systems and technologies to communicate smoothly.

INSPIRE Standards: Extend interoperability within the EU, standardizing data for seamless exchange across member states.

Promoting Collaboration:

OGC Standards: By being globally recognized, these standards encourage worldwide collaboration among various stakeholders in geospatial fields.

INSPIRE Standards: Target collaboration within the EU, creating a unified framework that aids in environmental, infrastructure, and disaster management projects.

Enhancing Data Accessibility:

OGC Standards: Improve the ease of access to geospatial data through open protocols, supporting a broad spectrum of applications.

INSPIRE Standards: Increase accessibility in the EU by standardizing web services and metadata catalogs, making spatial information easily discoverable and usable.

Supporting Policy Implementation:

OGC Standards: Offer a technical basis for aligning geospatial data with policy requirements and regulations.

INSPIRE Standards: Demonstrate how policy-driven standards can lead to uniform spatial data infrastructures across the EU.

Enabling Innovation:

OGC Standards: Provide a platform for creativity, enabling the development of novel applications and services utilizing geospatial data.

INSPIRE Standards: Encourage innovative solutions to societal and environmental issues within the EU through a shared spatial information infrastructure.

In summary, interoperable standards from OGC and INSPIRE play a critical role in the geospatial domain, supporting global and regional cooperation, enhancing data access, aiding policy compliance, and driving innovation. These standards create a unified and efficient **framework for the exchange** and utilization of geospatial data, underscoring their importance in the advancement of geospatial technologies and applications.

3.2 Standards for data model and encoding

Geospatial data encoding involves representing geographic information in a format that can be easily stored, accessed, processed, and shared. Various encoding formats have been developed to cater to different needs, such as efficient data storage, ease of sharing over the web, interoperability between different systems, and support for complex geospatial analysis. Figure 1 provides an overview of these encoding standards. Here is a list of common geospatial data encoding formats:

GML (Geography Markup Language): An XML grammar by the OGC for expressing geographical features and modeling geographic systems.

KML (Keyhole Markup Language): An XML notation for geographic visualization developed for Google Earth.

GeoJSON: Encodes geographic data structures using JavaScript Object Notation (JSON), supporting geometries and properties.

WKT/WKB (Well-Known Text/Binary): Textual and binary formats for representing vector geometry objects and spatial reference systems.

Shapefile: A popular vector data format for GIS, developed by Esri, describing vector features like points, lines, and polygons.

GeoPackage: An OGC standard using an SQLite database for storing and transferring geospatial information.

GPX (GPS Exchange Format): A light-weight XML format for interchanging GPS data between applications and web services.

NetCDF (Network Common Data Form): Supports creating, accessing, and sharing array-oriented scientific data, ideal for multidimensional spatial data.

HDF (Hierarchical Data Format): Designed to store and organize large amounts of numerical data, including complex scientific datasets.

CSV with Geospatial Extensions: Uses extensions, like WKT for geometry columns, to include geospatial data in CSV files.

CityGML: Stores digital 3D models of cities and landscapes, detailing geometrical, topological, semantic, and appearance properties.

GeoTIFF: An extension of TIFF for storing georeferenced imagery and elevation models.

JPEG 2000 (Part 2): Supports georeferencing for spatial raster imagery encoding.

Esri Grid: A raster GIS file format by Esri for representing geographic data.

DEM (Digital Elevation Models): Represent the Earth's surface elevation in various formats like USGS DEM and SRTM.

Multiband Raster Formats: Support different spectral frequencies or datasets, including GeoTIFF and NetCDF.

ECW (Enhanced Compression Wavelet): A high-compression raster format for large imagery datasets, optimized for aerial and satellite imagery.

MrSID (Multiresolution Seamless Image Database): Compresses geospatial raster imagery with lossless and lossy options.

ASCII Grid: A simple text format for representing raster data, often used for elevation models.

COG (Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF): Optimizes GeoTIFF files for cloud storage and access, supporting efficient data retrieval over the network.

Zarr: Stores chunked, compressed, N-dimensional arrays, suitable for high-dimensional geospatial datasets.

TileDB: Manages large-scale, high-dimensional, and sparse array data in the cloud, supporting diverse data types.

Parquet: An efficient, columnar storage format for large tabular datasets, including those associated with geospatial data.

ORC (Optimized Row Columnar): Offers efficient data storage and processing, useful for large-scale geospatial features.

GeoParquet: Extends Parquet to include geospatial vector data support, enabling spatial indexing and queries.

STAC (SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog): Standardizes geospatial asset metadata structure and querying, enhancing data discovery in the cloud.

COPC (Cloud Optimized Point Cloud): An extension of the LAS format for 3D point cloud data, optimized for cloud access.

These formats and cloud-optimized technologies are essential for leveraging cloud environments' scalability and computational power, facilitating efficient geospatial data management and analysis across various applications.

The above listed format are **just a first screening** , that will be integrated with more in dept analysis in the following chapters related to OGC standards and applicability of good practices, leading to a final set of formats to rank via Multi-Criteria Assessment choose considering the capability to support cloud-based solutions, the need for web interoperability, and the focus on formats that have achieved wide adoption or are emerging as standards in the field.

3.3 OGC Standards for data exchange – Services and API

Several OGC standards for data exchange exist. Former Web-service standards (WXS) are based on KVP/GET POST/XML requests and responses, while the more recent family of OGC API standards make use of RESTful and JSON. We will start with the WXS standards and then introduce the API standards.

OGC WFS

The OGC Web Feature Service (WFS) is a standard protocol for serving and querying geographic feature data over the web. WFS enables clients to request and retrieve vector-based geographic data, such as points, lines, and polygons, in a standardized and interoperable manner. The key capabilities of WFS are:

Interoperability: One of the primary strengths of WFS is its role in promoting interoperability. WFS provides a standardized interface for accessing geospatial vector data, allowing different systems and applications to exchange and work with spatial information seamlessly.

Real-time Data Access: WFS allows for real-time access to geospatial vector data. This is crucial for applications where up-to-date information is essential, such as emergency response systems, transportation monitoring, and other dynamic spatial scenarios.

Data Filtering and Querying: WFS supports powerful filtering and querying capabilities. Clients can request specific subsets of feature data based on spatial extent, attribute values, or other criteria. This enables clients to filter and retrieve only the data they need, reducing unnecessary data transfer over the network.

Standardized Output Formats: WFS uses standardized output formats, such as Geography Markup Language (GML), for representing geospatial features. This ensures consistency and compatibility across different systems that support the standard.

Transactional Capabilities: WFS supports transactions, enabling clients to perform operations like insert, update, and delete on the underlying geospatial database. This is valuable for applications where data editing and maintenance are crucial.

Integration with Other OGC Standards: WFS can be integrated with other OGC standards, such as Web Map Service (WMS) and Web Coverage Service (WCS), providing a comprehensive suite for accessing and working with different aspects of geospatial data.

OGC WFS is a powerful and widely adopted standard for accessing geospatial vector data over the web. Its strengths lie in interoperability, real-time data access, and transactional capabilities.

OGC WMS

The OGC Web Map Service (WMS) is a standard protocol for serving and requesting georeferenced map images over the web. WMS allows users to access maps from a variety of sources and overlay them with other geospatial data to create composite maps for visualization and analysis. The key capabilities of OGC WMS are:

Map Image Serving: WMS allows servers to generate map images dynamically based on client requests. These images can represent various geospatial data layers, such as satellite imagery, topographic maps, administrative boundaries, and more.

Integration with GIS Software: WMS is widely supported by Geographic Information System (GIS) software and mapping applications. Users can easily integrate WMS layers into their GIS projects and workflows, enhancing the accessibility and usability of geospatial data.

Versatile Visualization: WMS enables users to visualize geospatial data in a variety of formats and styles, including raster images, vector overlays, and thematic maps. This versatility makes it suitable for a wide range of applications, from simple map display to complex spatial analysis.

Dynamic Map Generation: WMS allows servers to generate map images dynamically in response to client requests. This capability enables users to access up-to-date maps with the latest geospatial data, without the need to store pre-rendered map tiles.

Layered Architecture: WMS supports a layered architecture, allowing users to overlay multiple map layers and customize the appearance of the map. This flexibility enables users to create composite maps tailored to their specific needs and preferences.

OGC WMS is a widely adopted standard for serving and requesting georeferenced map images over the web, with strengths in versatile visualization and dynamic map generation.

OGC WCS

The OGC Web Coverage Service (WCS) is a standard for serving and accessing multidimensional raster data over the web. It enables clients to request and retrieve coverages, which represent data in the form of maps, images, or other spatially referenced data structures. The key capabilities of OGC WCS are:

Multidimensional Data Support: WCS is designed to handle multidimensional raster data, which can include not only spatial dimensions (e.g., x, y) but also additional dimensions such as time, depth, or spectral bands. This makes it suitable for accessing data cubes, time-series data, and other multidimensional datasets.

Support for Different Data Formats: WCS supports various raster data formats, including GeoTIFF, NetCDF, and other common formats used in geospatial applications. This flexibility allows servers to provide data in formats that best suit the needs of the client applications.

Flexible Data Retrieval: WCS allows clients to request specific subsets of raster data based on spatial and temporal parameters, resolution, and other criteria. This flexibility enables efficient data retrieval and reduces unnecessary data transfer over the network.

OGC WCS is a valuable standard for accessing multidimensional raster data over the web, with strengths in providing access to complex raster datasets and flexible data retrieval.

OGC API – Features

The OGC API — Features (formerly known as WFS 3.0) is a modern standard for accessing and manipulating geospatial feature data over the web (OGC 2022a). It provides a more flexible and lightweight approach compared to previous versions of WFS, with a focus on simplicity, efficiency, and interoperability. Key capabilities of OGC API – Features are:

Resource-Oriented Architecture: OGC API — Features adopts a resource-oriented architecture, where each resource represents a collection of geospatial features. Resources are accessed using Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs), making it easy to work with feature data in a RESTful manner.

Core and Extensions: The standard consists of a core specification that defines basic functionality for accessing feature data, along with optional extensions that provide additional capabilities, such as transactions, filtering, and pagination. This modular approach allows implementations to support a subset of features based on specific requirements.

Support for Various Data Formats: OGC API — Features supports various data formats for representing environmental data, including standard formats such as JSON and XML, as well as specialized formats specific to environmental data types. This ensures compatibility and flexibility in data exchange and consumption.

Simplified Querying: The standard provides a simplified querying mechanism for retrieving feature data based on spatial and attribute filters. Clients can specify query parameters using URL query parameters, allowing for easy customization of data retrieval operations.

Asynchronous Operations: OGC API — Features supports asynchronous operations, allowing clients to perform long-running tasks, such as data processing and analysis, without blocking the server. This enhances scalability and responsiveness, particularly in scenarios involving large datasets or complex spatial queries.

Hypermedia Controls: The standard includes hypermedia controls in responses, enabling clients to discover and navigate related resources dynamically. This facilitates the creation of more interactive and adaptable web-based applications that can adapt to changes in data structure or server capabilities.

Modern Web Technologies: OGC API — Features leverages modern web technologies such as RESTful APIs, JSON, and HTML, making it well-suited for integration with web-based applications and services. This enables developers to build rich and interactive geospatial applications that can run in web browsers and other client environments.

OGC API — Features is a modern standard for accessing and manipulating geospatial feature data over the web, offering simplicity, flexibility, and interoperability.

OGC API Tiles

The OGC API — Tiles is a standard that provides a standardized approach for accessing and serving tiled map data over the web (OGC 2022b). It builds upon the principles of the OGC API family of standards, aiming to simplify the delivery and consumption of tiled map content. Key capabilities of OGC API – Tiles are:

Tile-Based Approach: OGC API — Tiles follows a tile-based approach to serving map data, where maps are divided into small, pre-rendered images called tiles. These tiles are organized into a hierarchical grid structure and can be retrieved individually based on their tile coordinates (zoom level, row, and column).

Tiling Schemes and Coordinate Systems: The standard supports various tiling schemes and coordinate systems for representing tiled map data, including popular schemes such as XYZ (Web Mercator), TMS (Tile Map Service), and WMTS (Web Map Tile Service). This ensures compatibility and flexibility in tile generation and consumption across different systems and applications.

Support for Vector Tiles: OGC API — Tiles extends beyond raster tiles to support vector tiles, which contain geometric and attribute data representing map features. Vector tiles offer advantages in terms of scalability, styling flexibility, and interactivity, making them increasingly popular for web-based mapping applications.

Scalability and Performance: The tile-based approach of OGC API — Tiles improves scalability and performance by pre-rendering map data into small, reusable tiles. This reduces server

load and bandwidth consumption, resulting in faster map rendering and improved user experience, particularly for large-scale maps and high-traffic applications.

Flexibility and Interoperability: OGC API — Tiles supports various tiling schemes, coordinate systems, and tile formats, offering flexibility and interoperability in tile generation and consumption. This enables developers to choose the most suitable approach for their specific use case requirements and ensures compatibility with existing tile-based mapping tools and services.

The OGC API — Tiles is a versatile standard for serving and consumption of tiled map data over the web, offering a simplified, scalable, and interoperable approach to tile-based mapping.

OGC API – EDR

OGC API for Environmental Data Retrieval (EDR) is a standard for accessing and retrieving environmental data over the web (OGC 2022c). Key capabilities of OGC API EDR are:

Focus on Environmental Data: OGC API EDR focuses specifically on providing access to environmental data, which may include data related to air quality, water quality, weather, climate, soil, biodiversity, and other environmental parameters.

Data Retrieval and Querying: The standard provides mechanisms for retrieving environmental data and performing queries to filter and refine the data based on specific criteria. This allows users to request data for a particular location, time period, parameter, or other relevant attributes, facilitating tailored data retrieval.

Specialized for Environmental Data: OGC API EDR is tailored specifically for accessing environmental data, providing dedicated functionality and capabilities to meet the unique requirements of environmental data users and applications.

OGC API EDR is a promising new standard for accessing environmental data over the web, offering a specialized and interoperable approach to data retrieval.

In conclusion, **the OGC API standards are modern tools** for data-exchange in a resource-oriented way using hypermedia controls. On the downside, the API standards possibly have a limited adoption, resulting in fewer implementations, supporting tools and documentation.

3.4 OGC Standards for finding data

The Catalog Service for the Web (CSW) is an OGC Web Service that provides the capacity to query a collection of metadata and find the data or the services that the user requires.

The OGC API – Records Standard is an alternative to CSW that uses the aforementioned resource-oriented architecture. It gives a URL to each and every metadata/data record stored in the catalog, making it compliant with the FAIR sub-principle “F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.”

OGC CSW

The OGC CSW is a standard for discovering, querying, and managing metadata about geospatial resources over the web. CSW enables users to search for geospatial data, services, and other resources based on various criteria, such as keywords, geographic extent, or temporal coverage. The key capabilities of OGC CSW are:

Metadata Discovery: CSW facilitates the discovery of geospatial resources by providing access to metadata catalogs. These catalogs contain descriptive information about datasets, services, and other resources, making it easier for users to find relevant data for their needs.

Querying Capabilities: CSW supports powerful querying capabilities, allowing users to search for resources based on specific criteria such as keywords, geographic extent, temporal coverage, and metadata properties. This enables precise and efficient searches, even across large metadata collections.

Integration with Discovery Tools: CSW can be integrated with discovery tools and client applications to provide users with a unified interface for searching and accessing geospatial resources. This integration enhances the usability and accessibility of metadata catalogs.

Comprehensive Metadata Discovery: CSW enables users to discover a wide range of geospatial resources, including datasets, services, maps, and other assets. This comprehensive coverage makes it a valuable tool for finding relevant information in geospatial data infrastructures.

OGC CSW is a valuable standard for discovering and querying metadata about geospatial resources over the web, with strengths in comprehensive metadata discovery and flexible querying capabilities.

The OGC WXS standards are widely used, versatile tools for data exchange. However, users should be mindful of potential complexities for simpler use cases and performance considerations when dealing with large datasets.

Figure 1: OGC standards architecture diagram (OGC).

Figure 2: Loose confederation approach (OGC).

3.5 Standards for data processing

The OGC API – Processes is a standard which supports the execution of computing processes and the retrieval of metadata describing the purpose and functionality of the processes over the web in an interoperable way (OGC 2021b). Typically, these processes execute well-defined algorithms that ingest vector and/or coverage data to produce new datasets. The standard defines a flexible interface to define process inputs and outputs. Processes can be executed in a synchronous or an asynchronous mode, allowing to run complex algorithms with a long response time. Triggered processes are registered as jobs of which users can request the status and the job result after finalization.

There are several core advantages of using OGC API Processes:

- Users do not need deep knowledge of the individual processes to run them
- Users do not need to provide the necessary hardware to run the processes
- It is easier to do processing next to the data, especially for large datasets
- It is easier to chain processes

3.6 Interoperability standards in the DIRECTED RWLs – Outcomes from the questionnaire

Participants in the Real World Labs have been invited to answer a survey on interoperability. The survey has been designed to identify gaps, challenges, and potential strategies to enhance interoperability within the realms of early warning systems, DRR, and climate change, how they are utilized and shared across different platforms and organizations.

The survey results provide insights into various aspects of data interoperability standards across different organizations. Here's a summary based on the initial overview of the data:

Organizations: The responses come from various organizations, which range from governmental agencies to private environmental consultancies, involved in managing and responding to environmental and climatic challenges.

Primary Areas of Operation: Respondents' organizations operate in several areas, notably water management (Gewässerverband) and DRR, with activities extending to emergency management, public awareness, and civil protection planning.

Types of Data Used: There's a mention of both meteorological and hydrological data usage among the respondents, highlighting the importance of environmental data in their operations. Some responses indicate a broad engagement with data types relevant to weather, climate, and water environments.

Interoperability Concerns: At least one organization explicitly states not having a dedicated team or individual for addressing interoperability concerns, suggesting that interoperability might be a shared responsibility or not explicitly focused on within some organizations.

Data-Related Challenges: The challenges mentioned range from managing large datasets and understanding the historical context behind data to standardizing data from various sources. This reflects common issues in handling, organizing, and utilizing geospatial data effectively.

Data Sharing and Commercialization: Responses hint at a mix of sharing upon request, with tools like WebGIS being used for open data sharing, and commercialization not being a primary focus for some. This suggests varied approaches to data dissemination and utilization among the organizations.

These outcomes, despite partial, propose the need for interoperable data standards in environmental and DRM domains. The survey highlights the diverse challenges organizations face regarding data management, the importance of meteorological and hydrological data, and the strategies for data sharing and commercialization. The absence of dedicated teams for

interoperability in some organizations points to potential areas for improvement in managing and standardizing geospatial data for broader and more effective use.

The survey on data taxonomy and interoperability aimed to identify existing gaps, challenges, and opportunities within the RWLs operating under the DIRECTED project. It focused on understanding the current state of data standards, usage, and the perceived benefits of achieving higher levels of standardization and interoperability. This chapter delves into the survey's findings, highlighting critical insights into data types used, existing interoperability concerns, and the strategic advantages of standardizing taxonomies.

1. Overview of Data Usage in RWLs

The survey captured responses from a diverse array of organizations involved in environmental management, emergency response, and climate adaptation. Key data types utilized across these organizations include:

- **Meteorological Data:** Used to inform weather predictions and climate-related decision-making.
- **Hydrological Data:** Critical for water management, flood prediction, and assessing the impacts of rainfall on river systems.
- **Geographical Information System (GIS) Data:** Widely used for spatial analysis and linking data to specific locations, facilitating detailed geographical assessments.

The findings indicate a robust engagement with environmental data, underscoring its importance in informing DRR and CCA activities. However, the data also revealed significant variations in how these data types are managed and utilized, pointing to inconsistencies that may hinder broader interoperability efforts.

2. Interoperability Challenges

A notable challenge identified in the survey is the lack of dedicated personnel focusing on interoperability within some organizations. This points to a broader issue of interoperability often being a shared responsibility rather than a clearly defined role, leading to gaps in strategic oversight and execution.

Additional challenges highlighted include:

- **Managing Large Datasets:** Organizations face difficulties in handling and processing large volumes of data, which can complicate efforts to standardize and integrate these datasets across platforms.
- **Historical Context and Data Standardization:** There is a need for better standardization of data sources to ensure consistency and reliability. This involves not just technical data formatting, but also aligning to semantic standards to ensure data is interpreted uniformly.
- **Data Sharing and Commercialization:** While many organizations are willing to share data, approaches vary, ranging from open WebGIS tools to more restrictive, request-based access. The inconsistency in data-sharing practices further complicates efforts to achieve interoperability.

3. Taxonomy Discrepancies and Benefits of Standardization

Respondents were asked about areas where taxonomy discrepancies are most prominent. The most frequently cited areas include crisis communication, where differing terminologies can lead to misunderstandings and slow response times.

The survey participants recognized several benefits of establishing a standardized taxonomy in DRR and CCA, including:

- **Improved Understanding and Coordination:** A common taxonomy can foster a shared understanding among diverse stakeholders, facilitating more effective communication and collaboration.
- **Enhanced Data Integration:** Standardized taxonomies enable easier integration of data from different sources, enhancing the ability to conduct comprehensive risk assessments and develop cohesive strategies.
- **Streamlined Processes:** By reducing ambiguities in data interpretation, standardized taxonomies can streamline decision-making processes, making it easier to deploy resources effectively during crises.

4. Recommendations for Enhancing Interoperability

Based on the survey findings, several recommendations emerge for advancing interoperability in the RWLs:

1. **Developing Dedicated Interoperability Roles:** To address the gaps in oversight, organizations should consider appointing dedicated teams or roles focused on data standardization and interoperability.
2. **Promoting Common Standards and Best Practices:** Efforts should be made to adopt and promote common standards, such as those from the OGC and FAIR principles, across all participating organizations.
3. **Enhancing Data Sharing Mechanisms:** There is a need for more consistent data-sharing protocols that balance openness with security and privacy considerations. This could include expanding the use of APIs and standardized web services to facilitate easier data access and integration.
4. **Training and Capacity Building:** Providing training on data standards and interoperability best practices can help equip stakeholders with the skills needed to implement these frameworks effectively.
5. **Leveraging Technology for Real-Time Data Integration:** To overcome the challenge of large datasets, leveraging cloud-based solutions and real-time data processing technologies can enhance the scalability and responsiveness of data systems used in DRR and CCA.

The survey underscores the importance of interoperability and standardized taxonomies in enhancing the effectiveness of DRR and CCA initiatives. By addressing the identified challenges and implementing the recommended strategies, RWLs can improve their capacity to manage and utilize data in ways that are more integrated, efficient, and impactful. This

alignment will ultimately contribute to building a more resilient data ecosystem capable of supporting diverse stakeholder needs in the face of climate-related challenges.

Data Types Usage Statistics:

The percentages represent how frequently each data type is used among the organizations surveyed:

- Meteorological Data: 38.7% of respondents use meteorological data, while 61.3% do not.
- Hydrological Data: 35.5% use hydrological data, with 64.5% not using it.
- GIS Data: 35.5% use GIS data, while 64.5% do not.
- Remote Sensing Data: 29.0% of respondents use remote sensing data, with 71.0% not using it.
- Demographic Data: 22.6% use demographic data, while 77.4% do not.
- Natural Hazard Data: 29.0% use natural hazard data, and 71.0% do not.
- Exposure Data: 22.6% use exposure data, while 77.4% do not.
- Risk Data: 25.8% use risk data, with 74.2% not using it.

Data Formats Usage Statistics:

The percentages represent how frequently various data formats are used among the organizations surveyed:

- NetCDF, GeoTIFF, HDF (Scientific Formats): Used by 35.5% of respondents, while 64.5% do not use these formats.
- Shapefile, GeoJSON, KML/KMZ (GIS Formats): Used by 38.7% of respondents, with 61.3% not using these formats.
- CSV/TSV (Spreadsheet Formats): Used by 38.7% of respondents, while 61.3% do not use these formats.
- Other Formats: No responses indicated the use of other unspecified formats.

Standardized Data Exchange Protocols Usage Statistics:

The usage of standardized data exchange protocols is less common among the surveyed organizations:

- OGC WMS (Web Map Service): Used by 16.1% of respondents, while 83.9% do not use this protocol.
- OGC WFS (Web Feature Service): Used by 9.7% of respondents, with 90.3% not using it.
- OGC WCS (Web Coverage Service): Used by 3.2% of respondents, with 96.8% not using this protocol.
- Other Protocols: There were no responses indicating the use of other protocols.

These statistics indicate a significant opportunity for increasing the adoption of standardized data formats and protocols across organizations engaged in DRR and CCA activities. Enhanced usage of these standards can improve data interoperability and integration, which are critical for effective DRM and climate adaptation strategies.

4. Replicability of good practices

A relevant aspect of the stocktaking for interoperability in DIRECTED is the evaluation of “the replicability of available good practices, such as UNEP Preview, Copernicus, DesInventar Sendai, EU’s DRMKC Risk Data Hub, EFAS, GLOFAS, Danube Reference Data and Services Infrastructure, EM-DAT, IdroGEO”. The purpose of this chapter is to present the method and the results of this specific evaluation.

4.1 Evaluation method

The first step in the process was the selection of “available good practices”. With DIRECTED being a European project, it seemed logical to include many CCA or DRR-related data sources with continental coverage or specifically addressing European stakeholders. Consequently, while searching for examples of good practices, the principal platforms investigated were those of the European Union’s Copernicus program (<https://www.copernicus.eu/en/>). There are mainly six collections, called **Copernicus Services**:

- Atmosphere
- Marine
- Land
- Climate Change
- Security
- Emergency

Atmosphere, or more exact the EU Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS), is dedicated to trace gases and radiation, the drivers of climate change. Among its many offers are data on air quality, the ozone layer and UV radiation, surface fluxes, and climate forcing. We focused on the satellite-derived fire activity analyses and the CAMS global biomass burning emissions based on fire radiative power (GFAS output) from the buffet of options, because dealing with wildfires is closely related to both CCA and DRR.

The marine service provides multidimensional, “zoom-able” views of ocean model outputs showing currents, temperature layering, salinity, wave heights of the planet’s major hydrosphere compartments, but was not considered due to the inherent land orientation of DIRECTED and its case study regions.

Land means the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) and contains geographical information on land cover and land use, elevation and ground motion, phenology and surface energy fluxes; in general features characterizing Earth’s surface. As static data like elevation models might be less interesting for CCA and DRR, we selected two different soil water index products, a high-resolution one for Europe, and a comparably coarse one with global coverage, because soil humidity could be a drought indicator and an input to hydrological modelling used in CCA studies. Satellite altimeters contribute river and lake water levels, valuable input to hydrological modelling. Snow water equivalents can be used to validate hydrological models, too, but in case of quick or heavy accumulations traffic and other

warnings (avalanche risk, exceedance of load carrying capacity of roof structures, etc.) could be triggered for DRR.

The climate change service could definitely inform CCA with its information about past, present and future climate – besides lots of textual information in form of bulletins and reports, at its core there is the **Climate Data Store (CDS)** maintained in cooperation with the European Centre on Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). It is very likely the most voluminous data offering among the Copernicus services. Special thematic applications range from the “monthly climate explorer for COVID-19” over “extreme precipitation statistics for Europe”, the “Date of birch pollen season onset from 2010 to 2019 derived from reanalysis”, and “Thermal suitability for fish species habitat” to “Heat wave days and heat related mortality for nine European cities derived from climate projections”, and there are many more. However, we decided against including any CDS service, because most data offered are either basic research products like raw climate reanalysis model outputs, far from CCA/DRR practitioners' needs, or already represented by products we included from other channels, for instance about soil humidity, erosion, or fire weather. Generic climate reanalysis data was considered from GeoSphere Austria (see below).

Security relates to surveillance of the EU borders over land and water, support of security actions, and related research and development. The nature of the subject requires confidentiality about the services provided under this umbrella; open for the public remain principally just a few infographics and other summarized information about migration and EU law enforcement. It is obvious that nothing from the security service fit into our evaluation.

An optimal DRR match can however be stated for the products of Emergency, the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS). It starts with risk and recovery mapping, immediate response information collected and presented by a task force that can be activated by member states facing a large-scale disaster. International rescue teams entering the scene are guided by their actual situation maps based on satellite imagery. The global human settlement layer might be static like an elevation map, but as a valuable basis for risk mapping it has nevertheless been included. Further CEMS products considered are the European and global flood awareness systems EFAS and GloFAS, the European Forest Fire Monitoring System (EFFIS), and the European and global drought observatories (EDO, GDO).

For a **second scoop of practice examples**, we researched warning portals of national hydrometeorological services and civil protection agencies. The selection of countries was guided by the location of the Real World Labs in DIRECTED. Included are weather warnings of the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), the German Weather service (DWD), GeoSphere Austria (formerly ZAMG), and the Hungarian Meteorological Service (OMSZ). By chance, Meteoalarm, a joint presentation of weather warnings from EUMETNET, an association of European weather authorities, was discovered and added to the pool. From the flood watch and alert portals, eHYD run by Austria's agricultural ministry, and Hydroinfo of the Hungarian Hydrological Forecasting Service were considered as well as Disaster Warnings from Germany's Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance (BBK) and the Civil Protection Directorate of the Hungarian Ministry of the Interior.

Not matching the original intent of finding warning and alert platforms were two data portals which had nevertheless additionally been selected: INCA and other gridded meteorological data products by GeoSphere Austria and the Water Website of the National Water Directorate General of the Hungarian Ministry of the Interior.

Finally, there were the **data providing platforms** already identified from the proposal stage such as EFAS and GloFAS, the UNEP Risk Project (formerly UNEP Preview), DesInventar

Sendai hosted by UNDRR, JRC's DRMKC Risk Data Hub, the Danube Reference Data and Service Infrastructure (albeit inoperable), the International Disaster Database EM-DAT, and IdroGEO, the Italian platform on hydrogeological instability.

In total, a number of 32 CCA and DRR-relevant information services, data platforms, or web portals had been collected.

After this initial screening phase, we translated relevant sources into **fact sheets** sharing a clearly arranged set of descriptive details. This collection of fact sheets which provided the basis for identifying common characteristics and individual details of the “best practice examples” is presented in the Annex 2.

4.2 Evaluation results

What do all the assessed platforms have in common, except from them having something to do with CCA or DRR? They serve in one or several ways as **data distributors**. The first collected evidence was that there are a lot of different kinds of data and a multitude of solutions to get them to the end-users. Beside first impression of lack of a real common standard, for data providing platforms, some recurring elements could soon be identified:

- Platforms **listing data sets** (and ideally also their metadata) with download options. This is the way for accessing the gridded map and model output data from the EU Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS), ECMWF and Copernicus Land or the water level time series also distributed by Copernicus Land. Just to name a few, because this kind of distribution is very common.
- Slippy **web map services** which do not allow for any other downloads than screenshot images. Examples are EUMETNET's Meteoalarm, the civil protection alerts distributed by Germany's Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance (BBK), and generally most warning or alert services. It seems they see no value in or are even afraid of keeping past warnings accessible.
- **Combinations** of the above:
 - Real combinations, where you can zoom in on something on the web map, select it there and download the data behind, are relatively seldom. Respectively comfortable examples are Austria's hydrological data platform eHYD or ISPRA's IdroGEO, the Italian platform on hydrogeological instability.
 - Less integrated web map services whose databases are offered from separate websites are probably more frequent, and in these case the accompanying website is hardly ever linked or even mentioned in the web map view. Among these not-so-good practice examples are the Fire activity analyses map viewer of CAMS, the flood awareness systems EFAS and GloFAS whose maps are stored on the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS), or the clickable warning map of the German Weather Service (DWD).

- **Query tools** for databases. This category has been observed with disaster catalogs: DesInventar, EM-DAT, and the catalog of the DRMKC Risk Data Hub.
- **API access** for large data sharing platforms. For instance, the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) provides API access, enabling programmatic retrieval of extensive climate datasets. This method supports advanced data analysis and integration by allowing direct access to large volumes of data without the need for manual downloading, potentially enhancing the utility and accessibility of climate information.

How **about the data formats and standards**? Although we just stated that “a lot of different kinds of data” were used, only few exceptions in our sample are not covered by the following list which therefore seems to resemble the actually **preferred formats**:

- Vector geodata
 - Shapefile
 - GeoJSON
 - georeferenced PDF
- Raster geodata (grids)
 - NetCDF
 - GRIB
 - GeoTIFF
 - PNG with georeferencing information
- Time series, tables, and unstructured data
 - Excel
 - CSV
 - Text

ESRI Shapefiles are still a very common de-facto standard for vector geodata despite it is a proprietary one. And most shapefiles of administrative regions or any other contiguous areas share a common weakness: Areas overlap, usually in narrow strips along boundaries, probably due to errors or uncertainties inherited from different surveys or the digitization of physical maps. Overlaps are not prevented by the structure in which shapefiles are organized internally. Each area is defined separately by a centroid point and a surrounding boundary. There might be practical advantages for separate area representations – but they are very rare.⁵

⁵ Topological GIS avoid involuntary overlapping areas by oriented boundary lines holding information about the areas to their left and to their right. Loading a shapefile with overlapping areas into an topological GIS (e.g. GRASS GIS) requires automated snapping of multiple, near identical boundaries, otherwise each tiny overlap generates an extra area, and trouble arises from double entries in the attribute database.

A more versatile vector data format based on SQL had been developed and recommended by the OGC. This open-source standard is **GeoPackage** (GPKG; current version 1.3.1, OGC 2021a), and it is the principal download option for joint products of the European mapping agencies (<https://eurogeographics.org>). They do however offer everything in shapefile format in parallel, and GPKG seems to be rather unknown beyond the core geodetic and surveying communities. Choosing GPKG instead of shapefiles for sharing DIRECTED's geodata would be fully in line with the idea of promoting open standards but restricting the data distribution to GPKG brings with it the risk of incompatibility to end-users' software and established work flows.

Not an OGC standard, but another, simple open geodata format which increasingly gains traction is **GeoJSON** (RFC 7946, 2016). In contrast to GPKG it is actually used by a couple of platforms – Copernicus Land (for lake and river water levels) and JRC's DRMKC Risk Data Hub in our sample.

Georeferenced PDFs (officially Geospatial PDF, Adobe specification included in ISO 32000-2, see also OGC 2011 for an alternative implementation) are regularly used for situation maps issued by disaster monitoring and response units, e.g. the Copernicus Emergency Management Service. As disaster recovery is time-critical and carried out by humans, the direct on-screen applicability and printability are more important than a potential reusability of the underlying raw geodata or machine readability. Consequently, metadata regularly appears in the form of human-readable legends and explanations within the graphic representation of the PDFs.

Web Feature Services (**WFS**) should also be mentioned as OGC-standardized web services for accessing vector geodata (OGC 2014), and there exist also protocols for vector tile servers. Such vector services are usually assessed through GIS applications and allow for customized downloads of spatial subsets, which are especially essential for very detailed online maps over large areas. For example, there would be no use in downloading the approximately 150 GB of OpenStreetMap (OSM) data of the whole world to render a map of a single province. We could however not identify any WFS service related to our sample of CCA and DRR-related portals.

For raster geodata, we observed **NetCDF** as well-established format, e.g., available for EFAS, GloFAS, CDS and EDO outputs, frequently used by ECMWF and other climate data providers, and the list of examples continues for some Copernicus Land products. The standard is quite versatile; data can be ordered along spatial and a time axis whose properties can be individually defined. A single file may contain several data layers, and there are standardized slots for metadata, e.g., the map projection used. The open NetCDF standards (Unidata n.d.) are hosted by the Unidata program at the University Corporation for Atmospheric Research (UCAR), and the OGC also work on sub-standards to NetCDF (see <https://www.ogc.org/standard/netcdf/>).

GRIB is a “GRIdded Binary format” developed by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) since 1985. Meanwhile, GRIB data are regularly distributed in a second version or “edition”, GRIB2 (WMO 2022). We observed this format with products available through the ECMWF CDF. Due to its historical ties to the aviation and meteorological communities and probably also limited versatility compared to NetCDF, GRIB and GRIB-compatible software are not so widespread. GRIB data offered for download should therefore always be

accompanied by an alternative NetCDF version of the same data, and this is actually practised at ECMWF CDF.

GeoTIFF is a very common raster format. As a georeferenced extension of the TIFF image format it may contain color tables for a pre-defined visual impression. Among the downsides is the restriction to a single layer of 2D geodata per file; there is however freedom regarding the numeric representation (e.g., byte, unsigned integer, double precision float) of the data. We observed this format being used for the Plant Phenology Index Seasonal Trajectories distributed by Copernicus Land, JRC's Global Human Settlement Layer, and the Global Drought Observatory (GDO). The selection of GeoTIFF may have been influenced by the low number of raster layers released in each of these applications (monthly, annual, or static). It is a public-domain standard whose legacy version (1.0) was formalized by the OGC in 2019 to become the official Geographic Tag Image File Format (GeoTIFF) v.1.1 standard (OGC 2019).

Georeferenced PNG images do not exist in the narrower sense, there is no extended PNG standard like GeoTIFF for TIFF images. A map delivered in the form of a PNG image may however have a defined correspondence between image pixels and geolocations. For example, the European Drought Observatory (EDO) offer the user to enter coordinates to exactly define the spatial dimensions of map images to download (however not via their interactive map viewer but an extra website, <https://edo.jrc.ec.europa.eu/edov2/php/index.php?id=1161>).

Standardized ways for downloading implicitly georeferenced image data (usually PNG), usually in the form of spatial subsets of the original map layer, are through a Web Map Server (**WMS**) or Web Map Tile Server (**WMTS**). The protocols for WMS and WMTS are maintained by the OGC (OGC 2006, 2010), and some platforms offer any or both of these services. Many GIS (e.g., QGIS) are able to automatically dispatch the required WMS/WMTS requests and data packages in the background while the user is shuffling a slippy map on the screen. Other GIS (e.g., GRASS) allow for a reproducible specification of geographical boundaries and spatial resolution of the image to be downloaded. Raster data distribution via WMS is for instance supported by EFFIS and the GDO.

Excel and CSV are the preferred formats for time series and tabulated data despite Excel being a proprietary standard which cannot be emulated in all details by open software. Which might not be a problem for most people, because the M— company inventing Excel successfully penetrated the global market for office software. However, CSV (Comma Separated Values) is to be preferred due to its openness and clear and simple structure defined in RFC 4180 (2005). It can easily be imported by all kinds of spreadsheet programs and machine applications but still be viewed and manipulated through a simple text editor, which is not possible for Excel files. A caveat is commonly observed divergences from the RFC standard; especially the delimiters might not be commas but semicolons or whitespace. It is however easy to adhere to the standard when producing CSV files.

Not observed among the sample portals and services were XML and JSON-formatted files; the latter are used for near real-time water level and discharge time series of some German gauging stations. River gauging data in general expose a wide variety of formats, common is just a preference for text files being extremely liberal interpretations of CSV. These occur to be ASCII, CP-1252, or UTF-8 encoded, may use any delimiters, missing-value codes, and commas instead of decimal points, and have arbitrary numbers of header lines of metadata. It might be a good idea to propose an international standard for hydrological time series files.

Text files or documents, even texts on websites, can be addressed as a last resort solution in case information is so overly complex that it resists being formatted along the lines of a data

standard. Examples populating this category are individual warning messages of civil protection agencies and the likewise event-specific assessments of the Copernicus Emergency Management Service. Text messages have however been analyzed in bulk by computer programs, for example regarding the extent and impact of flood events. A uniform character encoding (preferably UTF-8) is a minimum requirement for text exchange and machine readability, but also simple formatting standards below proper typesetting (e.g., Markdown in the CommonMark specification, <https://commonmark.org/>) might be considered for handling texts efficiently.

Finally, we assessed the **compliance with the FAIR principles**. Though they are quite detailed in their original formulation (Wilkinson et al. 2016), the major requirements for FAIR data can be broken down into three lines:

- Every data item should be accompanied by detailed metadata.
- Data and metadata should be registered and searchable through unique identifiers.
- Data and metadata should follow common standards to be machine-readable.

Note that **open access is not required** by the FAIR principles, but it is an objective of the DIRECTED project nonetheless. There were eight cases (25%) among our sample of 32 CCA and DRR-related platforms and services which cannot be accessed without registration. In addition, the data behind the web maps of the EU Risk Data Hub can only be assessed with an API key, single layers of the UNEP Risk Project can be held back by UN personnel, and EFAS flood forecasts of the past 30 days are not accessible to the public – nothing of that is unFAIR.

Regarding the FAIR requirements, it turned out that only the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service and parts of the climate data community (namely GeoSphere Austria) seem to have designed their data distribution accordingly. We graded the compliance with FAIR as follows:

- Very low – Ignorance towards FAIR principles, e.g., complete lack of metadata, no registration
- Low – Few requirements matched by chance, e.g., some metadata available, but not machine-readable and without unique identifiers
- Medium – Requirements partially matched, but notable gaps remain, e.g., non-comprehensive metadata
- High – Obvious awareness of the FAIR principles and a good achievement to keep them more or less completely
- Not applicable – Assigned to platforms only summarizing or merging data from different original sources

Our $n = 32$ sample was reduced by three cases “not applicable” to $n = 29$. Only seven cases (**24%**) reached the “**high**” grade indicating awareness of the FAIR principles, while 16 (55%) got either “low” or “very low” evaluations. Judging FAIR as a failed concept might however be too hasty. It has to be considered that the first formalization of the idea is just a few years old, and publishing a pile of non-uniform data in full compliance with all FAIR principles causes a considerable workload. The latter is however required for all results dissemination activities in DIRECTED project.

Cloud-optimized data standards play a critical role in DRR and CCA by facilitating efficient data storage, access, and processing capabilities (Figure 3). These standards are designed to maximize the benefits of cloud computing technologies, ensuring that data is easily accessible and usable for analysis, decision-making, and policy formulation in the face of climate-related challenges and disasters. While a direct list of such standards can be vast and evolving, here are some notable examples and concepts that are commonly recognized within the DRR and CCA communities for their cloud optimization and interoperability features:

Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG): A standard for storing geospatial data in a cloud-optimized way, enabling efficient access and sharing of large geospatial datasets over the web.

SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC): An open standard for exposing collections of spatiotemporal assets (e.g., satellite imagery) to make them more accessible and easier to consume in cloud-native environments.

NetCDF Cloud: An extension of the Network Common Data Form (NetCDF), a set of software libraries and machine-independent data formats that support the creation, access, and sharing of array-oriented scientific data, optimized for cloud storage and computing.

Zarr: A format for the storage of chunked, compressed, N-dimensional arrays that is designed for use in distributed and cloud-based storage environments, enabling high performance computing (HPC) and analysis.

GeoParquet: is an extension of the Parquet file format, a highly efficient, columnar storage format available within the Hadoop ecosystem. GeoParquet aims to optimize the storage and processing of geospatial data by leveraging Parquet's capabilities for compression and encoding schemes, which significantly reduce storage needs and improve access speeds. It supports storing geometric data types and associated attributes, making it highly suitable for cloud-based analytics and machine learning applications that require processing large volumes of geospatial data.

FlatGeobuf: is an open-source, performant, and interoperable binary file format for geospatial vector data. Designed to be fast and efficient for both reading and writing operations, it excels in scenarios requiring large datasets to be transferred over networks or processed in web applications. FlatGeobuf is characterized by its ability to handle complex geometries and attributes while maintaining a compact file size and quick access to individual features or subsets of the data. This format is particularly appealing for web-based DRR and CCA applications due to its speed and the ease with which it can be integrated into web GIS technologies.

Both GeoParquet and FlatGeobuf address specific challenges in the geospatial domain, such as the need for high performance, the ability to handle large datasets, and the requirement for interoperability across different systems and platforms. By adopting these formats, organizations engaged in DRR and CCA can enhance their capacity to analyze spatial data, model complex scenarios, and develop actionable insights more efficiently.

Figure 3: Cloud-Optimized Geospatial Formats (OGC).

Implementing these cloud-optimized data standards in the context of DRR and CCA allows stakeholders to leverage the scalability, flexibility, and computational power of cloud technologies. This ensures that data-driven responses to climate change and disasters are as timely, effective, and informed as possible.

In essence, analysis of data standards and interoperability across CCA and DRR platforms reveals a mixed landscape of data distribution methods and formats, reflecting both diversity and challenges in achieving a standardized approach. Despite initial perceptions of disparity, common distribution models and preferred data formats emerge, illustrating a move towards certain standards. However, issues like proprietary formats and compliance with FAIR principles indicate areas for improvement. Furthermore, Incorporating cloud-optimized standards into the interoperability framework not only aligns with the technological advancements but also underscores a commitment to improving the accessibility and utility of large climate datasets.

5. Ranking of interoperable standards

5.1 Introduction and scope of the Multi-Criteria Assessment

In the realm of Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and CCA, the effective utilization of interoperable data and geospatial standards has emerged as a pivotal factor in enhancing preparedness, response, and resilience efforts (Blanc et al., 2022, Al-Yadumi et al., 2021)

The intricate and dynamic nature of disasters and climate change impacts necessitates a comprehensive approach that integrates diverse data sources and standardization frameworks. In this context, this assessment endeavors to conduct an in-depth **analysis and ranking** of the existing interoperable data and geospatial standards pertinent to DRM and CCA. By evaluating their strengths, weaknesses, and overall effectiveness, this deliverable aims to offer valuable insights to policymakers, practitioners, and stakeholders, empowering them to make informed decisions and foster greater collaboration in addressing the complex challenges posed by disasters and climate change. The ranking process will be performed by exploiting the **FAIR** Data Principles, which emphasize making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, ensuring data quality and accessibility for all stakeholders. Additionally, **Multi-Criteria Assessment** will be employed to systematically analyze and weigh the various standards against a set of predefined criteria, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation that considers multiple dimensions and perspectives in the final ranking. Through this combined approach, we aim to establish a **robust and well-informed** framework for identifying the most effective and promising interoperable data and geospatial standards in the field of DRM and CCA.

5.2 Multi-Criteria Assessment based on the FAIR framework

5.2.1 Background on the FAIR framework

The FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles are essential for enhancing data usability and impact, particularly in DRM and CCA. These principles aim to improve the ways in which data is managed, shared, and used in scientific research and other data-driven domains.

- **Findability:** This principle emphasizes the importance of easily locating data. For geospatial data in DRM and CCA, this means metadata should be clearly and consistently structured to enable swift identification and retrieval of relevant datasets. This aspect is crucial for emergency response and strategic planning in disaster and climate change scenarios. (Percivall, 2010) discusses the application of open standards to enhance the interoperability of geoscience information, highlighting the importance of OGC standards in deploying a distributed information infrastructure for geosciences.
- **Accessibility:** The FAIR principles advocate for data to be easily accessible. In the context of DRM and CCA, this translates to making geospatial data readily available for stakeholders, enhancing real-time decision-making capabilities during critical events. (Bambacus & Percivaall, 2003) for example focuses on enabling decision support with geospatial standards, especially the increase in discovery, access, and use of remotely sensed data through geospatial interoperability specifications and standards.
- **Interoperability:** Perhaps the most crucial for DRM and CCA, interoperability ensures that data is structured using common standards, which is vital for integrating diverse datasets. This seamless exchange of information across platforms is key for holistic risk assessments and for understanding climate change impacts. (Giuliani & Peduzzi, 2011) introduces the PREVIEW Global Risk Data Platform, a geoportal offering free and interoperable access to global datasets on natural hazards and related risk, showcasing the use of OGC Web Services.
- **Reusability:** By making geospatial data reusable, the FAIR principles encourage ongoing research and innovation. This supports long-term strategic planning and development of more effective management strategies in DRM and CCA. (Miyazaki, Nagai, & Shibasaki, 2015) reviews geospatial information technology and collaborative data delivery for DRM, emphasizing the need for effective collaborations in data delivery.

The FAIR data principles have gained **significant prominence** as a guiding framework for enhancing the usability and impact of data in various domains, including DRM and CCA. At its core, the FAIR framework emphasizes the importance of making data easily findable through clear and standardized metadata, enabling efficient data discovery and retrieval. (Albrecht, 1999) provides a comparative study of approaches in the standardization of geospatial information, focusing on the issue of interoperability. The FAIR framework promotes Accessibility by ensuring that data is openly available and easy to access, removing barriers to entry for all stakeholders, from policymakers to researchers and practitioners. The Interoperability aspect of the FAIR principles is particularly crucial in the context of DRM and CCA, as it calls for data to be structured using common standards, facilitating seamless data exchange and integration across diverse platforms and systems. (Morris, 2010) explores the preservation of geospatial data and the connection with open standards' development, highlighting the role of OGC in ensuring data interoperability.

When applied to geospatial data within the context of DRM and CCA, the FAIR principles offer profound advantages in understanding and addressing the complex spatial dimensions of disasters and climate change impacts. Geospatial data, including satellite imagery, maps, and remote sensing data, play a critical role in disaster preparedness, risk assessment, and monitoring the effects of climate change. By adopting FAIR practices, geospatial data becomes more **easily discoverable**, allowing stakeholders to identify and access relevant datasets swiftly. The Accessibility aspect ensures that crucial geospatial information is available to stakeholders in Furthermore, adhering to the real-time, enabling rapid decision-making during disaster events and climate-induced crises.

Furthermore, adhering to the Interoperability principle promotes **seamless integration** of geospatial data from various sources, including governmental agencies, research institutions, and international organizations. This integration fosters a holistic understanding of disaster scenarios and climate trends, enabling a comprehensive assessment of risks and vulnerabilities. Through the FAIR framework, the geospatial data in DRM and CCA efforts becomes more Reusable, encouraging data-driven research, fostering innovation, and facilitating long-term analysis to develop more effective disaster management strategies and CCA measures.

In conclusion, the FAIR data principles provide a robust foundation for advancing the accessibility, integration, and utility of geospatial data in the context of Disaster Risk Management and CCA. By implementing these principles, stakeholders can unlock the full potential of geospatial information, allowing for data-driven decision-making, enhancing resilience, and ultimately contributing to more sustainable and effective approaches in addressing the challenges posed by disasters and climate change.

5.3 Purpose of the MCA

The primary purpose of the Multi-Criteria Assessment is to **methodically evaluate and rank** the diverse array of interoperable data and geospatial standards identified in the previous dedicated paragraph. Recognizing the critical role of such standards in DRM and CCA, this assessment aims to establish a well-informed and transparent framework for decision-making. By subjecting the identified standards to rigorous evaluation using the FAIR Data Principles and suggestions from detailed analysis carried on in the previous chapters and employing Multi-Criteria Assessment, the assessment seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of their strengths, weaknesses, and overall effectiveness in addressing the challenges of DRM and CCA. Through this systematic process, the assessment will ascertain **which standards align** most cohesively with the FAIR principles, offering enhanced Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of geospatial data. Additionally, the ranking allows stakeholders to identify exemplary models and **best practices** that have successfully demonstrated their efficiency and impact in the field. Ultimately, the aim is to furnish policymakers, practitioners, and stakeholders with actionable insights, enabling them to make **well-informed decisions** in adopting, implementing, and optimizing interoperable data and geospatial standards, thereby bolstering disaster resilience and CCA efforts.

5.4 Overview of the assessment process

The Multi-Criteria Assessment (MCA) process employed in this evaluation embodies a systematic and **objective approach** to rank the available interoperable standards for DRM and CCA. The MCA process involves a series of distinct stages that collectively contribute to a comprehensive analysis of each standard. Initially, a set of **relevant criteria** is carefully defined, capturing the fundamental attributes that are deemed essential for effective DRM and CCA applications. These criteria may include but are not limited to data accessibility, standard compliance, scalability, level of adoption, and overall performance. Subsequently, specific **weightings** are assigned to each criterion, reflecting their relative importance and impact on the overall assessment. During the assessment, the interoperable standards are evaluated against the defined criteria, and data is collected to quantify their performance scores in each category. The MCA process enables a **holistic consideration** of multiple dimensions, allowing

for a nuanced evaluation of each standard's strengths and weaknesses. By integrating the FAIR data principles into this process, the MCA ensures that emphasis is placed on factors like data findability, accessibility, and interoperability, which are crucial in geospatial data management for DRM and CCA. Ultimately, the MCA process culminates in the ranking of interoperable standards, offering stakeholders valuable insights into the most suitable and effective choices for promoting seamless data exchange, enhancing resilience, and facilitating CCA within the context of DRM.

In the context of a MCA for evaluating interoperable standards in DRM and CCA, several criteria can be considered to ensure a comprehensive and effective analysis. These criteria, drawn from the principles of good data management and interoperability practices, and embedding suggestions from the analysis carried on in the previous chapters, include:

Technical Criteria

T1 - Standard Compliance: Assess if the data format or standard complies with recognized international, national, or industry standards, such as those from the OGC, ISO/TC 211, or W3C.

T2 - Data Model Richness: Evaluate the capability of the data format or standard to represent complex geospatial and temporal information accurately and efficiently.

T3 - Interoperability: Determine the ease with which the data can be integrated with other data formats and systems, considering both syntactic (format) and semantic (meaning) interoperability.

T4 - Scalability: The ability of the data format or standard to handle varying volumes of data efficiently, from small datasets to large-scale geospatial data collections.

T5 - Performance: Evaluate the efficiency of the data format or standard in terms of processing speed, response time, and resource consumption.

Functional Criteria

F1 - Data Accessibility: The ease with which data can be accessed, including considerations for open access, authentication, and authorization mechanisms.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: The ability to easily exchange data among different systems, platforms, or applications without losing meaning or integrity.

F3 - Support for Metadata: The extent to which the data format or standard supports comprehensive metadata, facilitating data discovery, understanding, and use.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: The capacity to manage different versions of data and standards, allowing for backward compatibility and smooth transitions to new versions.

Usability Criteria

U1 - User Community and Support: The presence of a vibrant user community and availability of documentation, tools, and support services.

U2 - Ease of Implementation: Consideration of how easily the data formats and standards can be implemented in existing systems, including the availability of libraries, tools, and software support.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: The amount of training required for staff to effectively use and manage the data formats and standards.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: Evaluation of costs associated with adopting and using the data formats and standards, including licensing fees, implementation, and operational costs.

Sustainability and Evolution

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: Assess the long-term sustainability of the data format or standard, considering the backing organization's stability and the standard's adoption rate.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: The ability of the data format or standard to adapt to future technological changes and requirements.

5.5 Results of the MCA

Performing a Multi-Criteria Assessment (MCA) of all available data standards and formats suitable for DRR and CCA, based on the FAIR principles and additional criteria, involves a complex and detailed process far beyond the scope of this compendium. Even if a full MCA cannot be conducted directly here, a simple but effective approach can still be outlined in the following steps:

- 1) Define Scoring System: Establish a scoring system for each criterion (in this application a simple score from 1 to 5, where 1 indicates the lowest performance or capability and 5 indicates the highest).
- 2) Select Data Standards and Formats: Compile a comprehensive list of data standards and formats to be evaluated. This list includes identified relevant candidates from the previous analysis, such as GeoJSON, COG, NetCDF, FlatGeobuf, GeoParquet, KML, GML, Shapefiles, etc.
- 3) For each standard/format, assess the previously identified groups of criteria (Technical , Functional, Usability, and Sustainability), basing on literature review, expert judgement, and technical documentation to assign scores to each criterion for every data standard/format.
- 4) Weighting and Aggregation: if certain criteria are deemed more important than others for the specific DRR/CCA context, weights shall be assigned accordingly. Aggregate the scores, taking into account the weights, leads to derive an overall score for each standard/format. In this phase an equal weight has been assigned to all criteria.
- 5) Rank the data standards/formats based on their aggregated scores to identify the most suitable options for DRR and CCA.
- 6) Review and Decision-making based on the ranked list along with other qualitative considerations (e.g., specific project needs, technological constraints) to make informed decisions on which data standards/formats to adopt.

A full assessment is presented in **Annex 1** while the following table summarizes the results and scores for the different analyzed standards :

Table 1: Scores of MCA for the analyzed standards. Higher scores indicate better alignment with the FAIR principals and interoperability criteria.

Standard/Format	T 1	T 2	T 3	T 4	T 5	F 1	F 2	F 3	F 4	U 1	U 2	U 3	U 4	SE 1	SE 2	Final Score
OGC API	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	5	5	71
WFS	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	4	3	4	5	5	69
EDR API	5	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	4	4	3	4	5	5	66
GeoJSON	5	3	5	3	4	5	5	3	4	5	5	4	5	4	4	64
COG	4	4	4	5	5	5	4	4	3	4	3	3	5	5	4	62
WMS	5	3	5	3	3	5	4	4	5	5	5	3	5	4	3	62
NetCDF	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	5	3	3	5	4	4	62
GeoTIFF	5	4	5	3	3	4	5	4	3	5	5	3	4	4	3	60
GeoPackage	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	60
WCS	5	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	59
WMTS	5	3	4	5	5	4	3	3	4	4	4	3	4	5	3	59
STAC	4	3	5	4	N/A	5	4	4	4	5	4	3	5	5	4	59
GeoParquet	4	4	4	5	4	5	4	4	3	3	4	3	4	4	4	59
KML	4	4	4	3	3	5	4	4	3	5	5	3	5	4	3	59
Zarr	3	5	3	5	5	4	3	5	4	3	3	3	4	4	4	58
CSV	3	2	5	3	3	5	5	1	4	5	5	5	5	4	2	57
Shapefile	3	2	4	2	3	4	4	2	2	5	5	5	4	3	2	50
GRIB	4	2	3	4	4	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	4	4	2	45

The final assessment and ranking of geospatial data standards and formats, as presented in the updated matrix, reflect a comprehensive evaluation across a spectrum of criteria including standard compliance, data model richness, interoperability, scalability, performance, and other functional and usability aspects. Here are some observations and comments on the result and final ranking:

Top Performers: OGC API emerges as the highest-ranked standard with a final score of 71, highlighting its adherence to modern web standards, rich data model, and strong interoperability. This aligns with the current trend towards RESTful web services and leveraging OpenAPI for geospatial data interoperability. Following closely are WFS and EDR API, underscoring the importance of web services in geospatial data sharing and retrieval.

Highly Adopted and open Standards: GeoJSON, COG, and WMS also score highly, showcasing their widespread adoption and support within the geospatial community. GeoJSON's simplicity and effectiveness for web applications, COG's cloud optimization, and WMS's extensive use for map sharing and visualization are particularly noted.

Cloud and Web Optimization: The high ranking of COG and OGC API standards indicates a clear shift towards cloud-based geospatial data handling and RESTful APIs. These technologies are becoming increasingly important as GIS moves to the cloud, offering scalable, efficient access to geospatial data over the web.

Specialized Formats: NetCDF and GRIB, while more specialized towards scientific and meteorological data, still rank relatively well, reflecting their critical role in specific domains. Their design for handling complex, multidimensional data sets and meteorological information, respectively, ensures their continued relevance.

Emerging Technologies: STAC and GeoParquet show promising positions, indicating growing interest and adoption. STAC's focus on metadata and cataloging spatiotemporal assets and GeoParquet's optimization for handling large geospatial datasets in big data ecosystems highlight the evolving needs of the geospatial community.

Long-Standing Formats: Traditional formats like Shapefile and CSV, despite their limitations, remain relevant due to their simplicity, widespread adoption, and ease of use. However, their lower flexibility for future adaptation and inherent limitations in handling complex geospatial data needs are evident in their rankings.

Future Trends: The rankings suggest a trend towards formats and standards that support web and cloud optimization, interoperability with modern web technologies, and efficient handling of large and complex datasets. The adaptability to future technologies and requirements appears to be a key factor in the long-term viability and success of geospatial data standards.

In conclusion, the final ranking reflects both the current state and emerging trends in geospatial data handling, emphasizing the importance of interoperability, cloud optimization, and the ability to support complex data models. As the geospatial industry continues to evolve, the adoption of standards and formats that offer flexibility, efficiency, and compatibility with modern web technologies will likely increase.

6. Taxonomy and stakeholder collaboration/governance in the RWLs

6.1 What do users need?

When dealing with online platforms that host mostly qualitative content describing project challenges, enablers and outcomes, users face difficulties in discovering relevant content, that can be applied and reused. . The overwhelming amount of climate information online is also fragmented and disconnected leading to **"siloed"** information, **redundancy**, **replication** and a **lack of coordination and collaboration** within and between communities such as those in the DRR and CCA fields. These challenges identified through workshops during a Horizon 2020 project, PLACARD⁶ (see Figure 4) found that a key barrier to cohesion was the use of differing language and terminology in the CCA and DRR fields.

Key **reasons** for the lack of interoperability and connectivity between online qualitative content is that each platform uses its own taxonomy. Key terms, their definitions, and the general approach to their use may not be consistent across platforms in the same field (Barrott et al., 2020). Here, taxonomies have a key role to play in supporting adaptation learning and action. In the PLACARD project, increasing the discoverability of content in online CCA platforms was made possible by linking the keywords (or 'tags') that were used to describe knowledge products. The challenge was that many of these sites were not using **standardized taxonomies** to deepen such linkages.

Visualization of European adaptation actions and networks

By sourcing the information already available on various platforms and interconnecting it with help of tags, the **Climate Connectivity Hub** (Figure 5) makes existing information easier to access and increases the integration of knowledge. The Hub is a 'search and discovery' tool that helps users quickly and easily find information that they may not know exists. It helps to break down silos, avoid redundancy, replication and wasted resources, when people are not aware of parallel or complementary ongoing work. New and unexpected combinations of information can produce powerful policy-relevant insights, collaboration, dialogue and learning.

⁶ <https://www.placard-network.eu/>

Box 1: The unmet needs of users

During a workshop for the PLATform for Climate Adaptation And Risk reduction (PLACARD) in Brussels in 2017 national-level decision-makers from European governments, and representatives from NGOs shared the challenges they face daily when seeking information on CCA and disaster risk reduction. These issues are:

Discovering content – Participants struggle to quickly find relevant information, particularly given time constraints. When they find relevant information, they struggle to sort and filter material according to a target interest, such as a specific climate risk. They also struggle to find more detailed information on specific activities; for example, they can locate EU project descriptions, but not project activities or outputs. The content they uncover lacks evidence (such as evaluations of certain technologies) and examples (such as case studies). **The upshot: People do not find information about practices or approaches to emulate – or avoid.**

Understanding content – Participants struggle to find information that they can understand and interpret. The quality of data is not clear. The terminology used is often incomprehensible, relying too heavily on jargon and technical terms. **The upshot: People who find information struggle to understand it well enough to use it.**

Finding people, particularly peers – Participants struggle to find who is doing what, both where and how. Even when they find an overview of certain activities with a specific location and focus, they seldom find the names of people undertaking these activities, or ways to connect with them. As a result, participants are often unaware of relevant activities being undertaken in their region and/or in contexts relevant to their work. Participants want to connect with peers facing similar challenges to discuss relevant experiences and insights, but they often cannot locate them. **The upshot: People working in related fields do not make potentially valuable connections to help one another.**

Figure 4: The unmet needs of users (adapted from Barrott et. al., 2020).

The Hub provides a highly visual, interactive, and comprehensive overview of: CCA and DRR project outputs, methods, tools, and good practice insights (blue nodes in Figure 5); the organizations producing this knowledge (green nodes in Figure 5); and, associated keywords (tags) (orange node in Figure 5), the common element linking all the content together.

Such interoperability can be further enhanced with **specialized taxonomies** (see Section 6.2) that enables it to connect dispersed knowledge related to climate change, making this knowledge interoperable and usable, and facilitating its access to a very broad range of audiences. Content from the European Climate Adaptation Platform Climate-ADAPT⁷ is already connected to the Climate Connectivity Hub, and the goal to make networks of organizations and knowledge from the 150 demonstration regions interconnected in the

⁷ <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/>

Mission Implementation Platform, can be further facilitated using this visualization tool (and its taxonomy). The Hub links and visualizes data from several European and global platforms:

- CORDIS, a comprehensive database of EU Research and Development projects. Specifically, the Hub includes projects from Horizon Europe Cluster 5, Destination 1 focussed on climate neutrality and sustainable energy and EU Mission Adaptation projects.
- Global Resilience Platform, sharing innovative resilience solutions from around the world;
- Climate-ADAPT, the European Climate Adaptation Platform;
- PreventionWeb, the knowledge-sharing program of the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR);
- Eldis, covering development issues, and BRIDGE, a specialized gender and development service, both hosted by the Institute of Development Studies at the University of Sussex; and
- weADAPT, the global climate adaptation platform and network coordinated by SEI.

Data in the Hub is driven by the Climate Connectivity Taxonomy which builds on AR6 IPCC Glossary and the UNDRR-ISC Hazard Information Profiles. An API⁸ for the taxonomy is now available to enable platforms to increase their interoperability potential.

Figure 5: The search and discovery tool, the ClimateConnectivity Hub.

With respect to the models used in the Directed RWLs, **specialized taxonomies** can be co-developed with stakeholders (D4.2). Such co-development is important to not only identify key

⁸ <http://connectivity-hub.com/>

terms and those that are missing, but also to identify synonyms (where the same terms may be used differently) and co-develop scope notes (details on how the terms are used differently). This can be especially important in revealing different values, norms and socio-cultural characteristics which affect the interpretation and application of terminology.

Additionally, the Climate Connectivity Hub visualizes keyword tagging to connect currently "siloes" and fragmented knowledge and language from across different platforms and communities in an engaging and efficient way that also supports learning and collaboration. These keywords can also serve as the basis of a climate 'glossary' in the Data Fabric to promote a shared understanding of how (definitions) and why (scope notes) terminology is used in different ways in the climate change space. The keyword tags also support the discovery of 'related content'.

The screenshot displays the maia Directed Project interface. On the left, a search results panel for 'nature based solutions' shows 11 articles and 1 organization. It includes sections for 'Alternate name', 'Definitions', and 'Scope notes'. The 'Scope notes' section defines 'Nature-Based Solutions' (NBS) as a concept introduced to promote nature as a means for providing solutions to climate mitigation and adaptation challenges. The main area features a network diagram with a central yellow node labeled 'Keywords: nature based solutions'. This node is connected to several other nodes, including articles like 'Promoting climate resilient rural infrastructure in Northern Vietnam', 'Local Governments for Sustainability - Africa Secretariat', 'CLEVER Cities', and 'Restoration of the former Saltworks', as well as an organization 'Nature-based Solutions Initiative, University of Oxford'. A key at the bottom explains that the size of the circle represents the amount of connected content and provides instructions on how to interact with the nodes.

Figure 6: Translating keyword tags into a glossary offering definitions, related content and scope notes.

The Directed glossary will be co-developed with RWLs and this will be complemented with language and terminology used in the different models and tools that feed into the Data Fabric. The Hub will further develop existing taxonomies⁹ with definitions and scope notes and will visualize new datasets from other online platforms (Figure 6).

⁹ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1uPh00X7Et_E4Wsp4tqelurVzxPW4gsuEXY136qhXTzc/edit?tab=t.0

This combination of a visualization of the CCA and DRR actors, projects, and organizations combined with a visualization of how language and terminology is used by different communities and stakeholders will improve coordination, collaboration, and communication and help to accelerate learning and action.

6.2 IPCC seed glossary

In scoping the current state of adaptation taxonomies, a valuable resource in the form of an online **IPCC glossary**, the Collaborative Online Glossary System¹⁰ has emerged and is a seed taxonomy for the Climate Connectivity Taxonomy. This includes the glossaries of all IPCC Assessment Reports and Special Reports up to and including the sixth assessment cycle, and includes definitions, related, broader and narrower terms and translation into six UN languages. This credible source and extensive level of cross-referencing makes it ideal for use in online climate change platforms to enable them to adhere to FAIR principles, supporting interoperability, reusability and enhancing search and discovery through highly connected content. It also enables content to remain consistent with the latest science and to ensure all platforms are following the same global standards.

The online IPCC glossary is fully open source and accessible via a REST API. Additionally, this glossary is available in six languages (English, French, Spanish, Chinese, Arabic, and Russian). The tailoring or hybridization of the online IPCC glossary to address any gaps, e.g., using the EU Taxonomy, linking to the SDGs, urban adaptation or other sectors, could be an ideal scenario for further development. Furthermore, important social, risk, and governance elements that emerge from the Directed project, both through stakeholder engagement and through the evaluation of the various models and tools in use, can be verified with RWL stakeholders, to further enhance the Climate Connectivity Taxonomy, and thus address gaps in the IPCC glossary. Existing taxonomies that provide potential to address these gaps are the Society for Risk Analysis Glossary¹¹ and the Myriad glossary¹² that incorporate multi-hazard, multi-risk definitions and concepts. Taxonomies as described above could be further enhanced into ontologies and knowledge graphs, building on lessons learned through the development of the SustainGraph knowledge graph (Fotopoulou et al., 2022).

¹⁰ <https://apps.ipcc.ch/glossary/>

¹¹ <https://www.sra.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/SRA-Glossary-FINAL.pdf>

¹² https://www.myriadproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/D1_2_Handbook.pdf

6.3 Taxonomy and DRR/CCA governance practices in the RWLs – Outcomes from the questionnaire

Participants in the Real World Labs have been invited to answer a survey on Taxonomy and collaboration, aimed to identify gaps, challenges, and potential strategies to enhance interoperability within the context of early warning systems, DRR and CCA. The survey was designed to help understand how different organizations manage and standardize terminology to ensure clear communication and effective operation across various systems and sectors.

Participants to the survey belong to a diverse range of organizations. These include government agencies focused on territorial safety and civil protection, regional bodies responsible for environmental monitoring and management, and organizations involved in water management and research. Here's a revised summary of main outcomes in bullet points.

Common Vocabulary and Standardized Taxonomies:

- **Existence of Common Vocabulary:** Most organizations indicated that there is a common vocabulary in use to ensure consistent meaning across different systems. This is particularly prevalent in the fields of water management, civil protection, and emergency response, where standardized terminology is crucial for effective communication.
- **Standardized Taxonomies:** Several organizations confirmed the use of standardized taxonomies or terminologies, particularly those aligned with national directives and international standards such as those provided by DIN, WMO, and other recognized bodies.

Challenges in Integrating Data Due to Taxonomy Mismatches:

- **Understanding Across Disciplines:** One of the main challenges highlighted is the difference in terminology understanding across various disciplines, such as between hydrologists and firefighters. This often leads to communication barriers during critical operations.
- **Tool Discrepancies:** Another challenge mentioned was the incompatibility or discontinuation of certain tools, which complicates the integration of data from different sources. This is especially problematic when different organizations rely on tools that are not interoperable, or when tools are updated or phased out without proper synchronization.

Collaboration on Taxonomy Standardization:

- **Interorganizational Collaboration:** Some organizations reported active collaboration with other entities to standardize taxonomies, primarily through working groups and regular meetings. However, this was not universal, and several organizations indicated that they do not actively participate in such collaborations.
- **Updating Taxonomies:** The frequency of taxonomy updates varied, with some organizations conducting regular reviews every few years, while others did not have a formal process in place.

Cross-Organizational Collaboration:

- **Mechanisms in Place:** Several organizations reported having mechanisms in place for cross-departmental or cross-organizational collaboration, such as joint exercises, working groups, and shared data platforms. This collaboration is essential for ensuring that taxonomies remain consistent and that data can be shared effectively across different systems.

Benefits of Standardized Taxonomies:

- **Improved Communication:** A standardized taxonomy is seen as crucial for improving communication and understanding across different organizations, particularly in disaster response scenarios. This ensures that all parties involved have a clear and consistent understanding of the terms being used.
- **Operational Efficiency:** The use of standardized taxonomies also leads to greater operational efficiency, reducing the time needed to interpret data and make decisions during emergencies.

The survey responses underline the **importance of standardized taxonomies** and common vocabularies in enhancing interoperability across organizations involved in DRR and CCA. The challenges identified, such as the need for better cross-disciplinary understanding and the impact of tool discrepancies, highlight areas where further work is needed to improve data integration and collaboration.

7. Conclusions

The drive toward interoperability in Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) is a **complex, yet dynamic venture**, pivotal for effective data exchange and utilization. Rooted in the European Interoperability Framework and the EU eGovernment Action Plan, this effort aligns with the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) and INSPIRE initiative's goals, which emphasize the creation of a **cohesive data framework**, enhancing communication across various platforms and systems. The adoption of such standards is instrumental in not only ensuring the seamless exchange of spatial information among EU member states but also in setting **protocols** for the wider accessibility of geospatial data.

The methodology of this compendium, informed by **successful existing practices** and a Multi-Criteria Assessment, aims to distill best practices in interoperability tailored for DRR and CCA. This approach underscores the significance of multi-stakeholder collaboration in developing responsive data tools. As we move toward the replication of good practices, we envision a **user-friendly web map portal** with automatic language adjustment and integrated download options. Despite the resource-intensity of such platforms, a practical and minimalist interface is proposed, inspired by models like the Austrian climate grid distribution layout¹³.

In selecting data formats, the **FAIR** principle advocating for a formal, accessible, and widely applicable language guides our choices, balancing the use of proprietary formats against open standards. The emphasis is on **public sharing** of research findings, with a mindful approach to proprietary information, security, and sensitivities. This leads to a recommendation for a variety of data formats, such as GeoJSON and GPKG for vector data, NetCDF and GeoTIFF for raster data, and CSV for time series and tables, with text files likely utilizing Markdown, all encoded in UTF-8.

Furthermore, for **large datasets**, a strategy to provide accessible data segments is suggested, particularly for regional excerpts from extensive world maps. **Cloud-optimized** formats are recommended for their ability to leverage cloud technology's scale and efficiency, enhancing swift and informed data-driven responses.

The comprehensive analysis within this compendium has been distilled into criteria supporting the **Multi-Criteria Assessment (MCA)**, ensuring that the recommended standards align with interoperability's overarching objectives and embody efficiency, accessibility, and innovation. The MCA framework reflects the compendium's commitment to informed decision-making for the prioritization of interoperable standards within the **Data Fabric platform**.

Supplementing these findings, the outcomes of the **questionnaire** offer a lens into the current interoperability landscape within the DIRECTED Real World Labs, identifying existing gaps and opportunities for enhancement. The significance of standardized **taxonomies** and stakeholder collaboration is emphasized, advocating for unified taxonomies to bridge model gaps. The Climate Connectivity Hub is highlighted for its ability to amalgamate diverse knowledge sources through tagging, thereby improving information accessibility. A practical step forward is the creation of a **climate glossary**, standardizing terminology to facilitate clear communication, collaboration, and effective climate action, taking cues from the online IPCC glossary.

¹³ <https://data.hub.geosphere.at/group/raeumliche-daten>

In summary, this compendium advocates for an integrative approach to data standards and stakeholder engagement, essential for advancing DRR and CCA efforts. It calls for the harmonization of taxonomies and collaborative development to address the multifaceted challenges of climate change, with the ultimate goal of fostering a resilient, informed, and interconnected community poised for action.

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Annex 1 – Results of MCA analysis

Data /Standards Assessment

GeoTIFF

- T1 - Standard Compliance: 5 (An established, widely recognized standard)
- T2 - Data Model Richness: 4 (Supports a wide range of raster data types and metadata)
- T3 - Interoperability: 5 (Supported by virtually all GIS software)
- T4 - Scalability: 3 (Good for medium-sized datasets but not optimized for web or cloud at the same level as COG)
- T5 - Performance: 3 (Depends on file size and system; not optimized for partial reads like COG)
- F1 - Data Accessibility: 4 (Widely accessible due to universal support, though not as optimized for web as COG)
- F2 - Data Exchangeability: 5 (A de facto standard for raster data exchange)
- F3 - Support for Metadata: 4 (Extensive metadata capabilities)
- F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 3 (Stable, with minor evolutions over time)
- U1 - User Community and Support: 5 (Extensive support and usage across the GIS community)
- U2 - Ease of Implementation: 5 (Easy to use with widespread support in tools and libraries)
- U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 3 (Familiar to most GIS professionals, minimal training required)
- U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 4 (No licensing costs; efficient for storage but not as optimized for cloud scenarios as COG)
- SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 4 (Remains widely used, though newer formats like COG are becoming more relevant for cloud-based GIS)
- SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 3 (Somewhat flexible, but newer formats are better suited to modern web and cloud applications)

GeoJSON

- T1 - Standard Compliance: 5 (Widely recognized and used in web applications)
- T2 - Data Model Richness: 3 (Effective for simple to moderately complex vector geometries)
- T3 - Interoperability: 5 (Easily integrated with web technologies and GIS software)
- T4 - Scalability: 3 (Good for smaller datasets; large datasets may require optimization)
- T5 - Performance: 4 (Generally fast processing and transfer, especially for web applications)

- F1 - Data Accessibility: 5 (Simple to use and access in a wide range of applications)
- F2 - Data Exchangeability: 5 (Highly exchangeable due to its simplicity and support)
- F3 - Support for Metadata: 3 (Supports metadata but not as extensively as some other formats)
- F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 4 (Stable and widely adopted, with updates for ongoing support)
- U1 - User Community and Support: 5 (Very popular in web development and GIS communities)
- U2 - Ease of Implementation: 5 (Straightforward to implement with numerous libraries and tools)
- U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 4 (Easy for anyone with basic programming or GIS knowledge)
- U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 5 (No licensing fees, and its efficiency can reduce operational costs)
- SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 4 (Continues to be highly relevant for web GIS and applications)
- SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 4 (Adaptable and widely supported in evolving web technologies)

Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG)

- T1 - Standard Compliance: 4 (Builds upon the GeoTIFF standard)
- T2 - Data Model Richness: 4 (Supports rich raster data, optimized for cloud)
- T3 - Interoperability: 4 (Widely supported, especially in cloud environments)
- T4 - Scalability: 5 (Excellent for large datasets, cloud-optimized)
- T5 - Performance: 5 (Optimized for fast, partial data access in the cloud)
- F1 - Data Accessibility: 5 (Direct, efficient access to data stored in the cloud)
- F2 - Data Exchangeability: 4 (High, especially within cloud-based and modern GIS systems)
- F3 - Support for Metadata: 4 (Supports extensive metadata, crucial for cloud operations)
- F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 3 (Format is relatively stable, with incremental improvements)
- U1 - User Community and Support: 4 (Growing rapidly as cloud GIS becomes more prevalent)
- U2 - Ease of Implementation: 3 (Ease of use for those familiar with cloud environments, slightly steeper learning curve for others)
- U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 3 (Requires understanding of cloud storage concepts and COG specifics)
- U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 5 (Reduces storage and bandwidth costs by enabling partial data access)
- SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 5 (Increasingly important as GIS moves to the cloud)
- SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 4 (Designed with future cloud technologies in mind)

NetCDF

T1 - Standard Compliance: 4. NetCDF aligns with standards for data representation, supported by scientific and standards organizations.

T2 - Data Model Richness: 4. Supports complex, multidimensional data structures ideal for scientific data representation.

T3 - Interoperability: 4. Designed for portability and accessibility across different platforms, enhancing interoperability.

T4 - Scalability: 5. Efficiently stores and manages large datasets, supporting chunking and compression.

T5 - Performance: 4. Based on the HDF5 data model, offering improved data access speeds and compression.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 4. Self-describing format includes metadata, improving accessibility with tools available in numerous languages.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 5. Widespread adoption in scientific communities, adhering to common conventions for data exchange.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 4. Supports extensive metadata, including standardized information for climate and forecast data.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 4. Evolves over time with active maintenance, introducing features like hierarchical data organization.

U1 - User Community and Support: 5. Benefits from a robust user community, with extensive resources and support available.

U2 - Ease of Implementation: 3. Requires understanding of data models and conventions but supported by comprehensive documentation.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 3. Familiarity with multidimensional data beneficial, with documentation and examples facilitating learning.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 5. Open-source and freely available, contributing to reduced storage and processing costs.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 4. Expected to remain key for scientific data sharing, given its widespread adoption and active development.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 4. Demonstrates adaptability to new scientific and technological requirements, allowing for future enhancements.

GeoPackage

T1 - Standard Compliance: 4. GeoPackage is an OGC standard, ensuring compliance with international geospatial standards.

T2 - Data Model Richness: 4. Supports both raster and vector data, as well as complex spatial features and attributes.

T3 - Interoperability: 4. Designed to be used across various platforms and software, enhancing data sharing and compatibility.

T4 - Scalability: 4. Efficient storage and handling of large datasets due to its database structure.

T5 - Performance: 4. Provides fast data access and query performance, benefiting from the SQLite database's optimization.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 4. Enables direct access to geospatial data through SQL queries, making data retrieval straightforward.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 4. As an OGC standard, it is widely supported and easily exchanged between different GIS systems.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 4. Supports extensive metadata for datasets, facilitating comprehensive data documentation and discovery.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 4. While the format itself is stable, managing version control of data within a GeoPackage requires external tools or careful data management practices.

U1 - User Community and Support: 4. Growing adoption and support within the GIS community, with increasing resources and documentation available.

U2 - Ease of Implementation: 4. Supported by many GIS software packages, making it easy to adopt and integrate into existing workflows.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 4. Familiarity with SQL and database concepts is beneficial, but many GIS platforms abstract these complexities for the user.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 4. Open standard with no licensing fees, and its efficiency can reduce storage and processing costs.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 4. Backed by the OGC and adopted by a wide range of software providers, ensuring its continued relevance and use.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 4. Its structure allows for extensions and adaptations to meet evolving geospatial data needs and technologies.

GRIB

T1 - Standard Compliance: 4. GRIB is an international standard for weather data, endorsed by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO).

T2 - Data Model Richness: 2. Designed to encapsulate gridded data, supporting a wide range of meteorological data types and complex spatial/temporal structures.

T3 - Interoperability: 3. Highly specialized for meteorological data, ensuring good interoperability within weather-related applications.

T4 - Scalability: 4. Efficiently stores large volumes of data, well-suited for global weather systems over extended periods.

T5 - Performance: 4. Optimized for fast reading and writing, enabling efficient processing and dissemination of weather data.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 2. Requires specialized software or libraries, given the binary format of the data.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 2. Widely exchanged and used among meteorological organizations and researchers.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 2. Contains extensive metadata, though understanding it requires familiarity with the standard.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 3. Has evolved over time to accommodate new requirements, with considerations for backward compatibility.

U1 - User Community and Support: 3. Widely used in the meteorology community, with ample support resources.

U2 - Ease of Implementation: 3. Requires specialized knowledge and libraries, but supported by numerous tools and libraries.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 3. Understanding meteorological concepts and GRIB specifics is necessary, though tools help abstract complexities.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 4. Efficient in storing meteorological data and open standard, making it cost-effective.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 4. Critical role in international weather prediction and research ensures its continued importance.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 2. Shows adaptability, with efforts to meet the growing and changing needs of the meteorological community.

Zarr

T1 - Standard Compliance: 3 (Not an OGC standard but recognized in scientific communities)

T2 - Data Model Richness: 5 (Excellent for complex, multidimensional arrays)

T3 - Interoperability: 3 (Specific to scientific and cloud computing applications)

T4 - Scalability: 5 (Designed for large-scale scientific datasets)

T5 - Performance: 5 (Optimized for fast, scalable access to big data)

F1 - Data Accessibility: 4 (Accessible, especially within its target domains like climate science)

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 3 (Good within ecosystems that support Zarr)

F3 - Support for Metadata: 5 (Extensive metadata capabilities)

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 4 (Actively developed with community input)

U1 - User Community and Support: 3 (Growing, particularly among researchers and data scientists)

U2 - Ease of Implementation: 3 (Requires specific libraries and understanding of data structures)

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 3 (Targeted at users with scientific and technical backgrounds)

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 4 (Can reduce data storage and processing costs for large datasets)

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 4 (Increasing relevance for big data and cloud computing)

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 4 (Designed to meet future data challenges)

GeoParquet

T1 - Standard Compliance: 4. Builds on Apache Parquet, leveraging established standards for data storage, with growing acceptance in the geospatial domain.

T2 - Data Model Richness: 4. Efficiently stores complex vector data, supporting spatial geometries and attributes effectively.

T3 - Interoperability: 4. Good interoperability with big data ecosystems, enhanced by GeoParquet's geospatial capabilities.

T4 - Scalability: 5. Inherits Parquet's excellent scalability, efficiently handling large geospatial datasets.

T5 - Performance: 4. Fast data access and efficient query performance, benefiting from columnar storage.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 5. Accessible using standard data processing tools that support Parquet, with geospatial extensions.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 4. Foundation in Parquet and adherence to common geospatial types enhance exchangeability.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 4. Supports comprehensive metadata, essential for geospatial data management and analysis.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 3. Ongoing evolution with potential for wide adoption and standardization in the geospatial community.

U1 - User Community and Support: 3. Interest and support growing in both the geospatial and big data communities.

U2 - Ease of Implementation: 4. Existing Parquet tools and libraries facilitate implementation, with additional geospatial considerations.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 3. Requires understanding of both Parquet and geospatial data concepts.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 4. Efficient storage and processing can reduce costs, especially in big data applications.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 4. Alignment with big data technologies suggests strong potential for growth and relevance.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 4. Built on a flexible, modern foundation, ready to adapt to evolving technologies.

SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC)

T1 - Standard Compliance: 4. STAC is a community-driven specification, increasingly interoperable with OGC standards.

T2 - Data Model Richness: 3. Focuses on metadata and cataloging spatiotemporal assets, rather than direct data storage.

T3 - Interoperability: 5. Facilitates discovery and access across different platforms and data types, enhancing geospatial ecosystem interoperability.

T4 - Scalability: 4. Lightweight and flexible, STAC scales well with dataset size and number.

T5 - Performance: N/A. Performance is dependent on implementation, as STAC deals with metadata and cataloging.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 5. Aims to make geospatial assets easily discoverable and accessible.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 4. Improves exchange of geospatial data through standard, accessible metadata formats.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 4. Enhances use and effectiveness of metadata for spatiotemporal resources.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 4. Actively developed with community input, ensuring it evolves to meet needs.

U1 - User Community and Support: 5. Quickly gained wide support and adoption across developers, companies, and organizations.

U2 - Ease of Implementation: 4. Simple and intuitive design facilitates straightforward implementation.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 3. Requires some understanding of JSON and metadata standards but is designed to be accessible.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 5. Enhances data discoverability and usability, potentially reducing data management and integration costs.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 5. Growing adoption and design flexibility suggest a significant role in future geospatial data discovery and management.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 4. Designed for adaptability to evolving geospatial data storage and analysis technologies.

OGC Web Map Service (WMS)

T1 - Standard Compliance: 5. WMS is an established OGC standard, ensuring interoperability across different GIS platforms.

T2 - Data Model Richness: 3. Focuses on delivering map images rather than raw data, offering visual representations.

T3 - Interoperability: 5. Widely supported across GIS software, allowing for seamless integration and map sharing.

T4 - Scalability: 3. Scalability may be limited by server capacity, especially for high-demand services.

T5 - Performance: 3. Performance varies based on server capabilities and map complexity, with caching improving responsiveness.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 5. Easy access to map visualizations via simple HTTP requests.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 4. Facilitates visualization by exchanging map images over geospatial data.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 4. Provides basic metadata about the map layers available through the service.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 5. WMS has evolved through versions, with active community development and maintenance.

U1 - User Community and Support: 5. Supported by a large community, with extensive documentation and examples.

U2 - Ease of Implementation: 5. Straightforward to implement WMS clients, supported by a wide range of libraries and tools.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 5. Relatively simple to use, requiring minimal specialized knowledge.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 5. Efficient map sharing and visualization without significant client-side resources.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 4. Remains relevant for map sharing and visualization as a foundational web service standard.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 3. The standard is mature, with further innovations pursued through newer standards like WMTS or OGC API.

Web Feature Service (WFS)

T1 - Standard Compliance: 5. As an OGC standard, WFS ensures broad interoperability for accessing geospatial features.

T2 - Data Model Richness: 5. Supports complex queries and transactions on geospatial features, offering access to raw vector data and attributes.

T3 - Interoperability: 5. A widely adopted standard that facilitates integration of geospatial features across different platforms.

T4 - Scalability: 4. Efficient at delivering vector data, though performance can vary with the complexity of queries and dataset size.

T5 - Performance: 4. Performance depends on implementation and accessed data, with optimization and indexing improving response times.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 5. Enables direct access to geospatial data, allowing for programmatic query and manipulation of feature data.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 5. Facilitates the exchange of geospatial features and attributes between systems.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 5. Provides detailed metadata about features, enhancing data discovery and usability.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 5. WFS has evolved through multiple versions, improving functionality and performance.

U1 - User Community and Support: 5. Benefits from strong support within the OGC and the broader GIS community.

U2 - Ease of Implementation: 4. Implementing WFS services and clients can be complex, requiring an understanding of geospatial data and web services.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 3. Effective use and implementation require familiarity with GIS concepts and web service integration.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 4. Provides significant value in enabling dynamic access to and manipulation of geospatial data, with potential higher costs due to implementation complexity.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 5. Continues to be crucial for web-based geospatial data sharing and manipulation.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 5. The evolution towards OGC API - Features indicates strong adaptability to new web technologies and user needs.

Web Map Tile Service (WMTS)

T1 - Standard Compliance: 5. WMTS follows OGC standards for serving geospatial map tiles, ensuring wide compatibility.

T2 - Data Model Richness: 3. Focuses on serving pre-rendered or dynamically rendered map tiles rather than raw geospatial data.

T3 - Interoperability: 4. The standardized approach to tile serving ensures WMTS can be easily integrated across different platforms and clients.

T4 - Scalability: 5. The use of tiles allows for efficient caching and distribution, supporting scalable web mapping applications.

T5 - Performance: 5. Serving tiles can be highly efficient, especially when the tiles are pre-rendered and cached.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 4. Tiles are accessible through standard web requests, simplifying the integration and use in web maps.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 3. While tiles are easily exchanged, they represent images rather than data with inherent geographic meaning.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 3. Metadata is limited to tileset descriptions and capabilities rather than detailed data descriptions.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 4. WMTS is relatively stable, with incremental improvements primarily focused on performance and scalability.

U1 - User Community and Support: 4. WMTS is well-supported by both open-source and commercial mapping tools, with a large user base.

U2 - Ease of Implementation: 4. Consuming WMTS services is straightforward, supported by many web mapping libraries.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 3. Integrating WMTS into applications is relatively easy, requiring minimal specialized knowledge.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 4. The efficiency of serving and caching tiles makes WMTS an economical choice for delivering map content at scale.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 5. The demand for efficient, scalable map tile serving continues to make WMTS a key component of web GIS.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 3. While the tile-serving concept remains robust, further innovations in web mapping may see WMTS evolve or integrate with newer standards.

OGC API

T1 - Standard Compliance: 5. Represents the next generation of OGC standards, focusing on RESTful web services and leveraging OpenAPI for interoperability.

T2 - Data Model Richness: 5. Supports rich data models and complex queries, adapting to modern web practices with the OGC API family.

T3 - Interoperability: 5. Highly interoperable and easy to use with modern web technologies, improving integration with other web services and platforms.

T4 - Scalability: 5. Leverages RESTful principles for scalable and efficient access to geospatial data over the web.

T5 - Performance: 5. Optimizes performance and user experience using modern web standards and protocols.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 5. Provides accessible and discoverable geospatial data services through familiar web patterns.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 5. Facilitates easy data exchange and integration in web applications and services.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 5. Emphasizes self-describing services with comprehensive metadata support.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 5. Modular nature allows for continuous improvement and extension to meet emerging needs.

U1 - User Community and Support: 4. Rapidly growing as the community adopts and implements these new standards.

U2 - Ease of Implementation: 4. Based on familiar web standards, but requires understanding of RESTful services and possibly OpenAPI.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 4. Approachable for developers familiar with web development, though some learning required to fully leverage capabilities.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 4. Adoption of web standards promises to reduce costs associated with developing and consuming geospatial web services.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 5. Positioned to be the future of geospatial web services, reflecting current web development trends.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 5. Modular and extensible design ensures adaptability to future technologies and requirements, maintaining relevance.

OGC Web Coverage Service (WCS)

T1 - Standard Compliance: 5. WCS is an OGC standard, ensuring interoperability across different geospatial data platforms and applications.

T2 - Data Model Richness: 4. Designed for retrieving geospatial data as "coverages", supporting rich, multidimensional raster datasets.

T3 - Interoperability: 4. Facilitates easy integration with other web services and GIS software, supporting widespread data exchange and manipulation.

T4 - Scalability: 4. Can handle large datasets efficiently, though performance scales with server capabilities and network conditions.

T5 - Performance: 3. Performance depends on the complexity of queries, the size of data being retrieved, and server optimization.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 4. Provides an interface for accessing raster data over the web, allowing users to specify the exact subset of data they need.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 4. Supports the exchange of raster data in various formats, enhancing data usability across different platforms.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 4. Services include descriptive metadata about the coverage data, facilitating discovery and use.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 4. WCS has evolved through versions to improve functionality and user experience, with active development and community support.

U1 - User Community and Support: 4. Strong support within the OGC and among GIS professionals, with extensive documentation and examples.

U2 - Ease of Implementation: 4. Requires understanding of the service interface and coverage concepts but is supported by numerous tools and libraries.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 3. Involves a learning curve related to web services and raster data handling.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 4. Enables efficient access to precise subsets of raster data, potentially reducing data storage and processing costs.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 4. Remains critical for geospatial data services, facilitating access to complex raster datasets.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 4. Continues to evolve, aiming to enhance performance, user experience, and integration with new data formats and web technologies.

OGC Environmental Data Retrieval (EDR) API

T1 - Standard Compliance: 5. EDR API follows modern web standards and OGC specifications for interoperability as part of the OGC API suite.

T2 - Data Model Richness: 4. Designed to access a wide range of environmental data types, supporting complex queries for specific data needs.

T3 - Interoperability: 5. Built for easy integration with web applications and services, leveraging RESTful principles and the OGC API framework.

T4 - Scalability: 4. Suited for both small and large-scale environmental datasets, the API design allows for efficient data retrieval.

T5 - Performance: 4. Optimized for quick access to environmental data, utilizing modern web technologies and data indexing strategies.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 5. Simplifies access to environmental data, allowing queries for precise information based on location, time, and parameters.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 5. Facilitates easy data exchange and integration into applications, supported by standard data formats and protocols.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 5. Provides comprehensive metadata to aid in data discovery, understanding, and utilization.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 4. Benefits from active development and community feedback as a new addition to the OGC API family, ensuring continual improvement.

U1 - User Community and Support: 4. The user community and support resources are growing, with increasing adoption and implementation examples.

U2 - Ease of Implementation: 4. Designed for ease of use with RESTful API principles, making it accessible to developers familiar with web services.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 3. Requires understanding of the API's capabilities and how to formulate queries but is designed to be developer-friendly.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 4. Enables targeted data retrieval, reducing unnecessary data transmission and processing, and improving efficiency in applications.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 5. Addresses a critical need for accessible environmental data retrieval, aligning with trends towards more modular and flexible web APIs.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 5. Well-positioned to adapt to new web technologies and data standards, ensuring relevance and utility in future environmental data services.

Shapefile

T1 - Standard Compliance: 3. While not an official standard of organizations like the OGC or ISO, Shapefile has become a de facto standard due to its widespread adoption.

T2 - Data Model Richness: 2. Supports basic vector geometries (points, lines, polygons) but lacks support for more complex structures and attributes compared to newer formats.

T3 - Interoperability: 4. Its wide adoption ensures good interoperability across almost all GIS software, though it may require conversion or supplementation for certain uses.

T4 - Scalability: 2. Suitable for small to medium-sized datasets; struggles with performance and manageability for very large datasets.

T5 - Performance: 3. Generally efficient for its intended scope of use but can be outperformed by newer formats, especially for large datasets.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 4. The format's simplicity and widespread support make it easily accessible for a broad range of applications.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 4. Its status as a de facto standard ensures high exchangeability across different systems and platforms.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 2. Limited support for metadata, often requiring separate files or conventions outside the Shapefile specification itself.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 2. The Shapefile format has seen little to no evolution since its inception, limiting its ability to adapt to modern geospatial data needs.

U1 - User Community and Support: 5. Extensive documentation, tools, and a large user base exist due to the format's long history and widespread use. U2 - Ease of Implementation: 5. Its simplicity and widespread support in software make it very easy to implement and use.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 5. Familiarity with Shapefile is common in the GIS field, requiring minimal additional training.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 4. No licensing costs and its effectiveness for a wide range of basic geospatial tasks make it cost-effective.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 3. Despite its limitations, the Shapefile format's widespread use ensures it will remain relevant for certain applications.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 2. The format's lack of evolution and inherent limitations restrict its flexibility to adapt to new geospatial data needs and technologies.

CSV (in Geospatial Context)

T1 - Standard Compliance: 3. CSV is a universal format, not specific to geospatial standards but can be adapted for geospatial use through conventions.

T2 - Data Model Richness: 2. While flexible, CSV is inherently limited in expressing complex geospatial data models directly within its structure.

T3 - Interoperability: 5. CSV files can be imported and exported by virtually all software, offering high interoperability for tabular data.

T4 - Scalability: 3. Suitable for small to medium-sized datasets; large datasets may become unwieldy and inefficient in processing.

T5 - Performance: 3. Performance is generally good for data reading and writing but can be impacted negatively as file size grows.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 5. CSV files are easily accessible and understood by a wide range of tools and users, making them highly accessible.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 5. The simplicity of CSV files makes them highly exchangeable, though spatial data requires additional conventions or context.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 1. CSV inherently lacks a mechanism for embedding metadata, making it challenging to include comprehensive spatial metadata directly.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 4. The basic nature of CSV means it's not subject to evolution in the same way as more complex formats but remains stable and widely used. U1 - User Community and Support: 5. The universal use of CSV ensures a vast user community and extensive support across different domains, including geospatial. U2 - Ease of Implementation: 5. CSV's simplicity makes it extremely easy to implement and use for a wide range of data tasks, including basic spatial data tasks.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 5. Due to its simplicity and widespread use, working with CSV requires minimal specialized training.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 5. CSV's simplicity and the absence of licensing fees make it a cost-effective option for data exchange and storage.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 4. CSV's simplicity and ubiquity ensure its long-term use, though it may be complemented or superseded by formats that better handle complex geospatial data.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 2. While CSV itself offers little in terms of adapting to new geospatial data needs, its data can often be migrated to more capable formats as needed.

KML (in Geospatial Context)

T1 - Standard Compliance: 4. KML is an OGC standard, ensuring interoperability across various platforms that support geospatial data.

T2 - Data Model Richness: 4. Supports a comprehensive range of geospatial visualization features, including placemarks, paths, polygons, and 3D models, with styling and rich multimedia content.

T3 - Interoperability: 4. Widely supported by geospatial software, allowing for seamless integration and sharing of geographic visualizations.

T4 - Scalability: 3. While KML files can handle complex datasets, large KML files may lead to performance issues in some Earth browsers.

T5 - Performance: 3. Performance is generally good for small to medium-sized datasets but can degrade with very large or complex KML files.

F1 - Data Accessibility: 5. KML files are easily accessible and usable across a wide range of platforms, enhancing the dissemination of geospatial information.

F2 - Data Exchangeability: 4. KML files are easily exchanged and shared, though their use is more focused on visualization than raw data exchange.

F3 - Support for Metadata: 4. Provides mechanisms for embedding descriptive information and metadata within the file, although not as extensive as some dedicated data formats.

F4 - Version Control and Evolution: 3. KML has evolved to support new features over time, though updates are not as frequent as some other web standards.

U1 - User Community and Support: 5. There's a strong community of users and developers, with extensive documentation and examples available.

U2 - Ease of Implementation: 5. Creating and using KML files is relatively straightforward, supported by many tools and libraries.

U3 - Training and Learning Curve: 3. While basic KML can be easy to produce, utilizing its full range of features requires a deeper understanding of the format and possibly XML.

U4 - Cost-Effectiveness: 5. As an open standard, KML does not incur licensing fees, and its effectiveness in visualizing geospatial data can enhance the value of geospatial projects.

SE1 - Long-Term Viability: 4. KML's role as a standard for geospatial visualization ensures its ongoing relevance, especially for applications requiring rich geographic content display.

SE2 - Flexibility for Future Adaptation: 3. While KML is somewhat adaptable, its focus on visualization may limit adaptation to new types of geospatial data analysis or modeling needs.

Annex 2 – Fact sheets

Fact sheets of the 32 tools and data platforms about natural hazards and risks assessed for their data formats and interoperability standards

1. EU Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS) · Fire activity analyses
2. CAMS through ECMWF · CAMS global biomass burning emissions based on fire radiative power (GFAS output)
3. Copernicus Land Monitoring Service · Soil Water Index 2015-present (raster 1 km), Europe, daily – version 1
4. Copernicus Land Monitoring Service · Soil Water Index 2007-present (raster 12.5 km), global, 10-daily – version 3
5. EU Copernicus Land Monitoring Service · Lake Water Level 1992-present (vector), global, Near Real Time – version 2
6. EU Copernicus Land Monitoring Service · River Water Level 2002-present (vector), global, Near Real Time – version 2
7. EU Copernicus Land Monitoring Service · Snow Water Equivalent 2006-present (raster 5 km), Northern Hemisphere, daily – ver. 1
8. EU Copernicus Land Monitoring Service · Plant Phenology Index Seasonal Trajectories 2017-present (raster 10 m), Europe, 10-daily
9. EU Copernicus Emergency Management Service · Risk and Recovery Mapping
10. EC's Joint Research Centre · Global Human Settlement Layer
11. EU Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) · European Flood Awareness System (EFAS)
12. EU CEMS · Global Flood Awareness System (GloFAS)
13. EU CEMS · European Forest Fire Monitoring System (EFFIS)
14. EU CEMS · European Drought Observatory (EDO)
15. EU CEMS · Global Drought Observatory (GDO)
16. EUMETNET · Meteoalarm
17. Danish Meteorological Institute · Warnings
18. German Weather Service · Warnings
19. Germany's Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance (BBK) · Warnings
20. GeoSphere Austria (formerly Zentralanstalt für Meteorologie und Geodynamik, ZAMG) · Weather warnings
21. GeoSphere Austria · INCA and other gridded meteorological data products
22. Austria's Federal Ministry for Agriculture, Forestry, Regions, and Water Management (BML) · eHYD

23. Civil Protection Directorate, Hungarian Ministry of the Interior · Event Map
24. Hungarian Meteorological Service (OMSZ) · Weather warnings
25. Hungarian Hydrological Forecasting Service · Hydroinfo
26. Hungarian Ministry of the Interior, National Water Directorate General · Water Website
27. UNEP Risk Project (formerly UNEP Preview)
28. UNDRR · DesInventar Sendai
29. EC's Joint Research Centre (JRC) · DRMKC Risk Data Hub
30. Danube Reference Data and Service Infrastructure (DRDSI)
31. Centre for Research on the Epidemiology of Disasters (CRED) · EM-DAT – The International Disaster Database
32. Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA) · IdroGEO – The Italian platform on hydrogeological instability

EU Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS) · Fire activity analyses	
Weblink	https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu/charts/packages/cams/products/fire-activity
Content	<p>Daily maps of fire activity measured by radiative power (W/m²)</p>
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	Global, continental and subcontinental maps (28 views) in different projections without scale
Time representation	Daily. The current day and 3–4 previous dates are available.
Data format, volume	<p>PNG images. approx. 6 MB/d for global, 1.5 MB/d for European coverage See CAMS globl biomass burning emissions for GRIB data</p>
Access restrictions	No
Access options	Either through website using menus for region and date or by direct image download. Download links with curl script example are provided.
Compliance with FAIR	Very low. Metadata and unique identifiers are missing.
Remarks	<p>The most intense fires are displayed in bright yellow to white colors and are therefore practically invisible on the white background used for land areas. As the maps provide only a coarse spatial orientation their value for DRR is very limited.</p> <p>For georeferenced data with 0.1 degrees spatial resolution see “CAM5 through ECMWF · CAM5 global biomass burning emissions based on fire radiative power (GFAS output)”.</p>

CAMS through ECMWF · CAMS global biomass burning emissions based on fire radiative power (GFAS output)	
Weblink	https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/cams-global-fire-emissions-gfas
Content	<p>Global georeferenced grids of the fire activity maps provided by CAMS (see Remarks below). These are output data of the CAMS Global Fire Assimilation System (GFAS). In addition to the radiative power, the wildfire fraction of the area observed, the fire-related emissions of 42 substances, and injection height parameters are included.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">GFAS emissions [g CO / m² / year]</p> <p>Illustration taken from Andela et al. (2013), https://www.ecmwf.int/sites/default/files/elibrary/2013/7707-assessment-global-fire-assimilation-system-gfasv1.pdf</p>
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	Regular latitude-longitude grid with a horizontal resolution of 0.1 degrees
Time representation	Daily from 2003 until present
Data format, volume	GRIB1, NetCDF in test mode. Approx. 25 MB per day and variable.
Access restrictions	Registration required
Access options	FTP via ftp://aux.ecmwf.int
Compliance with FAIR	Low. Found erroneous metadata in GRIB file, no unique identifier.
Remarks	See “EU Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS) · Fire activity analyses” for current map images of the radiative power.

Copernicus Land Monitoring Service Soil Water Index 2015-present (raster 1 km), Europe, daily – version 1	
Weblink	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/soil-moisture/daily-soil-water-index-europe-v1-0-1km
Content	<p>As the title suggests, though a satellite-based product covering only the top 5 cm of the soil profile.</p> <p>Example visualization from the Product User Manual, https://land.copernicus.eu/en/technical-library/product-user-manual-soil-water-index-version-1</p>
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	Geographical raster over Europe in WGS84 coordinates, resolution 1/112 degree (0.0089285714°) on both axes; 1 km is just the nominal resolution.
Time representation	Daily
Data format, volume	NetCDF v4, 80–100 MB per daily file
Access restrictions	EU Login required
Access options	
Compliance with FAIR	High. Extensive metadata in XML format, URN identifiers present.
Remarks	The most recent product usually has a time lag of 2–3 days to the current state.

Copernicus Land Monitoring Service Soil Water Index 2007-present (raster 12.5 km), global, 10-daily – version 3	
Weblink	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/soil-moisture/10-daily-soil-water-index-global-v3-0-12-5-km
Content	Global decadal composites of satellite-retrieved (top 5 cm) soil moisture status. For details see the Product User Manual: https://land.copernicus.eu/en/technical-library/product-user-manual-soil-water-index-version-3
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	0.1-degree grid in WGS84 coordinates. the 12.5 km are only a nominative value.
Time representation	Decadal
Data format, volume	NetCDF v4, 16–18 MB every 10 days
Access restrictions	EU login required
Access options	
Compliance with FAIR	High. Extensive metadata in XML format, URN identifiers present.
Remarks	See also “Static layers” data set.

EU Copernicus Land Monitoring Service Lake Water Level 1992-present (vector), global, Near Real Time – version 2	
Weblink	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/water-bodies/water-level-lakes-near-real-time-v2.0
Content	Lake water levels obtained by satellite altimetry
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	Lake surface, centroid location given in WGS84 coordinates
Time representation	Irregular, depending on the satellite overpasses. Usually at least once per week. Updates approx. two days after the most recent observation.
Data format, volume	GeoJSON. With only one observation every few days per virtual gauging station, the data volume is negligible.
Access restrictions	Login required
Access options	
Compliance with FAIR	High. Extensive metadata in XML format, URN identifiers present.
Remarks	There are no lakes from the Danube area included in this product.

EU Copernicus Land Monitoring Service River Water Level 2002-present (vector), global, Near Real Time – version 2	
Weblink	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/water-bodies/water-level-rivers-near-real-time-v2.0
Content	<p>River water levels obtained by satellite altimetry</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: small;">credits : CNES, Copernicus, Legos, CLS</p>
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	River cross-section, point location given in WGS84 coordinates
Time representation	Irregular, depending on the satellite overpasses. Usually at least once per week. Updates approx. two days after the most recent observation.
Data format, volume	GeoJSON. With only one observation every few days per virtual gauging station, the data volume is negligible.
Access restrictions	Login required
Access options	
Compliance with FAIR	High. Extensive metadata in XML format and URN identifiers present.
Remarks	With several hundred virtual stations in the Danube basin probably useful for bias-adjustment of the Danube model flood level outputs. For discharge calibration, rating curves would however also be needed for the same locations.

EU Copernicus Land Monitoring Service Snow Water Equivalent 2006-present (raster 5 km), Northern Hemisphere, daily – ver. 1	
Weblink	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/snow/snow-water-equivalent-v1-0-5km
Content	<p>Near realtime grids of snow water equivalent and its uncertainty</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Copernicus Global Land Service, 5km NH SWE variance, 20170210</p> <p>https://land.copernicus.eu/en/technical-library/product-user-manual-for-snow-water-extent-norther-hemisphere-5-km-raster</p>
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	0.05-degree grids in WGS84 coordinates. The 5 km are just a nominal resolution value. Latitudes are limited to 35–85°N.
Time representation	Daily, near realtime; irregular updates within 12 hours after new data become available.
Data format, volume	NetCDF v4, 55 MB per daily file
Access restrictions	EU login required
Access options	
Compliance with FAIR	High. Extensive metadata in XML format and URN identifiers present.
Remarks	Alerts could easily be derived (e.g. load-bearing capability exceedance of roof constructions, road blocking and avalanche risk warnings, etc.)

EU Copernicus Land Monitoring Service Plant Phenology Index Seasonal Trajectories 2017-present (raster 10 m), Europe, 10-daily	
Weblink	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/vegetation/high-resolution-plant-phenology-index-seasonal-trajectories
Content	<p>For each 10 m raster cell containing vegetation, the plant phenology development is modelled from Sentinel satellite images, i.e., the gaps between cloud-free observations are filled.</p> <p>Screenshot of the Cologne–Bergheim area for 21 May 2021</p>
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	10 m grids. Principally the Sentinel UTM tiling of the raw data, there are also post-processed products in ETRS89-LAEA projection.
Time representation	Decadal, production intervals are however for calendar years with releases in spring of the following years.
Data format, volume	GeoTIFF images of about 125 MB per tile (109.8 × 109.8 km)
Access restrictions	Login required
Access options	Besides the Plant Phenology Index, there is also a Vegetation Phenology and Productivity product from the same tool chain. Each product comes with a respective quality flag layer.
Compliance with FAIR	High. Extensive metadata in XML format and URN identifiers present.
Remarks	The product can be used to analyze very detailed drought effects on vegetation; the high resolution allows for crop-species specific assessments. Unfortunately the production cycle does not allow for near-realtime information.

EU Copernicus Emergency Management Service · Risk and Recovery Mapping	
Weblink	https://emergency.copernicus.eu/mapping/list-of-activations-risk-and-recovery
Content	<p>Individual regional in-depth post-event risk analyses for different kinds of recently observed disasters (floods, landslides, earthquakes, fires, etc.)</p> <p>Landslide susceptibility in the Naples area performed on ANN model</p> <p> ■ polygon layer of landslides (IFFI, n=277) ● point layer of landslides (CAFLAG, n=2337) </p> <p>Landslide susceptibility classes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Very high ■ High ■ Moderate ■ Low ■ Very low <p>Source: EMSN-142 – Post-disaster evaluation and preparedness analysis of landslide risk in Ischia, Italy. Final report, p. 47</p>
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	Varying, determined by location and size of the events covered
Time representation	Irregular, several weeks to months after the respective events
Data format, volume	Reports and/or maps in PDF format, discontinuously published
Access restrictions	None, except for triggering the service for new events
Access options	Downloads from website
Compliance with FAIR	Low. There are few metadata on the event webpages, identifiers (e.g. EMSN-142 in the example above) are not indexed for searching.
Remarks	There is a parallel rapid mapping service for actual disasters at https://emergency.copernicus.eu/mapping/ primarily intended to aid early response teams in their field operations.

EC's Joint Research Centre · Global Human Settlement Layer	
Weblink	https://ghsl.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datasets.php
Content	<p>Global high resolution grids containing quantitative information on built-up surfaces; average building heights, volumes, and functions; population; degree of urbanization; and some auxiliary data.</p> <p>Average building heights in Paris. Example image taken from page 28 (PDF page 33) of the data manual, https://ghsl.jrc.ec.europa.eu/documents/GHSL_Data_Package_2023.pdf</p>
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	Global, area-preserving grids in Mollweide projection. Principal raster resolution is 100 m, some layers are disaggregated to 10 m, and there are also some 1-km aggregations.
Time representation	Static layers of high recency (current release GHSL P2023), including some historic data starting in 1975 and extrapolations for 2025 and 2030.
Data format, volume	GeoTIFF tiles covering 1000 × 1000 km each in Mollweide projection. Global coverage of a single thematic layer demands 5–15 GB of storage space, a single tile usually less than 500 MB.
Access restrictions	No
Access options	Download via https://ghsl.jrc.ec.europa.eu/download.php
Compliance with FAIR	Medium. The data are indexed via PID and doi, and there are extensive metadata, albeit no machine-readable version of the latter.
Remarks	May be useful to assess risk exposure.

EU Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) European Flood Awareness System (EFAS)	
Weblink	https://www.efas.eu/en
Content	<p>Flood forecasts, precipitation fields and other real-time data (e.g. social network activity) concerning European floods</p>
Forecast or alert	Yes
Spatial representation	Many outputs are bound to LISFLOOD raster cells currently at 5 × 5 km spatial resolution (see example image of a forecast for the 4th August 2023 extreme flood in the Upper Sava River Basin upstream of Zagreb)
Time representation	Updates twice a day (nominally at noon and at midnight)
Data format, volume	Map viewer at https://www.efas.eu/efas_frontend/#/home EFAS partners also receive flood alert notifications.
Access restrictions	Real-time forecasts of the past 30 days are only available to EFAS partners, authorities with legal obligations to provide flood forecasting services or having a national role in flood risk management.
Access options	Multiple switches for information layers in the map viewer. Gridded data from the hydrological modelling can be downloaded through the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS).
Compliance with FAIR	Medium. The gridded data but not their metadata are registered by doi; only some metadata are contained in the GRIB and NetCDF files.
Remarks	The service is meant to provide additional forecast data to be integrated in the forecasts distributed by national or regional authorities and flood alert services. Avoiding public distribution of independent forecasts maintains coherent guidance during events.

EU CEMS · Global Flood Awareness System (GloFAS)	
Weblink	https://www.globalfloods.eu/
Content	<p>Global river runoff and flood data including medium-range forecasts</p>
Forecast or alert	Yes
Spatial representation	Point data and geographical 0.1-degree grids
Time representation	Daily status maps and forecasts (up to 30 days lead time)
Data format, volume	Map viewer, Free raster data in GRIB2-format available through ECMWF
Access restrictions	Map viewer only accessible for registered users
Access options	Flood severeness is estimated by yearliness categories. Multiple lead times are aggregated, and points with more concise hydrological information are flagged. One out of two different hydrological models (LISFLOOD, HTESSSEL) can be chosen as well as older model versions for comparison. Gridded data from the hydrological modelling can be downloaded through the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS).
Compliance with FAIR	Medium. The gridded data but not their metadata are registered by doi; only some metadata are contained in the GRIB and NetCDF files.
Remarks	Due to its spatio-temporal coarseness, GloFAS outputs might be more relevant to identify large-scale emergency conditions in remote countries than to provide detailed and accurate information on the local river system.

EU CEMS · European Forest Fire Monitoring System (EFFIS)	
Weblink	https://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/
Content	<p>Web map application showing fire danger, active fires, burnt areas, and past fire severities</p> <p>Among the EFFIS products are also online portals for fire news and statistics and fire weather forecasts.</p>
Forecast or alert	Only regarding fire supporting weather conditions
Spatial representation	Depending on the product: from a 0.1-degree-grid for fire weather down to about 0.4 arc seconds (~ 10 m) for fire severities.
Time representation	Daily updates. Historical data only accessible on request.
Data format, volume	Web portal. Raster images are also available via WMS. Directly downloadable are PNG images of the thematic layers in low resolution lacking projection information. Some data are only accessible on request.
Access restrictions	No
Access options	Switchable Layers in the web map viewer, download links, WMS
Compliance with FAIR	Very low. Data are being replaced daily, and previous versions are not accessible without human intervention. No indexing, no metadata on previous versions. Important information (e.g. map projection) is missing.
Remarks	Does not include actual forest fire warnings

EU CEMS · European Drought Observatory (EDO)	
Weblink	https://edo.jrc.ec.europa.eu/tumbo/edo/map/
Content	<p>Visualization of a 5 km grid showing seven different degrees or classes of drought severeness or recovery across Europe.</p>
Forecast or alert	Alert for regions highlighted in red. There is also a very coarse (one degree grid cells) three-months outlook for unusual wet or dry conditions.
Spatial representation	Based on the pan-European hydrological modelling with 5 km raster resolution.
Time representation	Decadal. There may be daily updates based on newly incoming data (cf. https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/european-and-global-drought-observatories/when-data-becomes-available-archive_en).
Data format, volume	Web maps (images) of which only non-georeferenced screenshots can be downloaded directly; there is however an extra interface for georeferenced image download.
Access restrictions	None
Access options	Multiple radio buttons for the different thematic layers. There is also an OWS (Open Geospatial Consortium Web Services) interface for georeferenced image download.
Compliance with FAIR	Moderate. Indexing seems to be missing, but there is a tool to indicate historical data availability and a metadata catalog leading to XML files for all kinds of data.
Remarks	There is no means to receive an alert automatically for a certain location. Compared to floods, droughts develop slowly so that such a feature would probably be of low importance, though.

EU CEMS - Global Drought Observatory (GDO)	
Weblink	https://edo.jrc.ec.europa.eu/tumbo/gdo/map/
Content	<p>Relatively coarse and simple drought impact maps together with a ranking of currently most drought-affected countries</p> <p>In addition, drought-constituting meteorological and soil-related variables and vegetation status can be shown.</p>
Forecast or alert	Quasi-alerts (“high drought risk”) for regions highlighted in red.
Spatial representation	Relatively coarse maps for continental views. Downloads are offered in 1-degree resolution.
Time representation	Decadal
Data format, volume	Online map viewer, only non-georeferenced images of the current view, can be downloaded from here. There is however also a WMS server for georeferenced images, and global and European layers are accessible in GeoTIFF and NetCDF formats. Volumes are moderate due to the coarse spatio-temporal resolutions.
Access restrictions	None
Access options	Multiple radio buttons for the different thematic layers. Georeferenced downloads only through connected websites.
Compliance with FAIR	Low. Indexing seems to be missing, and there are no machine-readable metadata except what is contained in the geodata formats.
Remarks	Gives a rough orientation of the current drought distribution on planet Earth. The affectedness of countries also considers their economic framework conditions. The locally perceived drought severeness may however, differ from what the map images suggest.

EUMETNET · Meteoalarm	
Weblink	https://www.meteoalarm.org
Content	<p>Slippy map of Europe showing areas with apparent weather dangers; clicking on the map opens detailed text warnings for the region specified.</p> <p>Warnings issued for 2023-11-17 one day ahead. Note the red “hurricane-like gusts” warnings in the southernmost parts of Germany while Switzerland issued no warnings at all, and Austria has just a low-level warning of strong wind.</p>
Forecast or alert	Warnings collected from European weather services
Spatial representation	Administrative sub-regions of European countries
Time representation	Discontinuous updates (may be sub-daily). The user can choose between different lead time windows.
Data format, volume	Web interface.
Access restrictions	None
Access options	There is no download option for the displayed warnings or other meteorological data yet, but the EU project RODEO (2023–2025) is advertized to improve the situation, see https://rodeo-project.eu
Compliance with FAIR	Not applicable. This is only a viewer presenting a mosaic composed from different original data sources.
Remarks	This portal merges the weather warnings issued by 31 European weather services. It fills a relevant gap. A shortcoming are however unreasonable steps in severeness levels at national boundaries. In some countries, the spatial resolution is coarser than what is published via their national services' websites or alert systems.

Danish Meteorological Institute · Warnings	
Weblink	https://www.dmi.dk/varsler/
Content	<p>Slippy map showing areas with apparent weather dangers; clicking on the map opens detailed text warnings for the point specified.</p> <p>Aktuelt varsel - næste 48 timer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Varsling om kraftig regn <p>Der er DMI varsel for kraftig regn over Sjælland fra i nat og frem til torsdag eftermiddag.</p> <p>Kraftig regn betyder at der kan falde mere end 30 mm på 24 timer. De store nedbørmængder kan desuden medføre lokale oversvømmelser, da jorden flere steder er vandmættet og vandstanden allerede er høj i mange vandløb.</p> <p>Et lavtryk er under udvikling over Nordsøen og ventes fra sent i aften og i nat at tage en bane ind over den sydlige del af landet. Torsdag morgen ventes lavtrykket at ligge nær Lolland og Falster og herfra fjerner det sig kun langsomt mod sydøst til det nordvestlige Polen, hvor det forventes torsdag aften. Det tilhørende regnområde bevæger sig i aften og i nat ind over det meste af landet, bortset fra det vestlige og nordlige Jylland. Ud på natten og i morgen tidlig når ligger lavtrykket tættest på, kan nedbøren en overgang også gå over i slud eller meget våd tøsne.</p> <p>Vi følger situationen og opdaterer efter behov.</p> <p>Udsendt af vagthavende meteorolog Steen Hermansen den 15.november kl. 09.50</p> <p>LES MINDRE</p>
Forecast or alert	Warnings based on 48-hour forecasts
Spatial representation	Coast sections and the 98 Danish municipalities
Time representation	Discontinuous updates every few hours, according to the situation.
Data format, volume	Web interface.
Access restrictions	None
Access options	<p>Clicking at a certain location in the map opens a detailed forecast with the warnings relevant for that point.</p> <p>Maps of single warn items (heat, rain, wind, etc.) can be switched.</p>
Compliance with FAIR	Very low. A corresponding text about warning items and thresholds may represent the metadata. Indexing, machine-readability and persistence are however completely lacking.
Remarks	There are no download options.

German Weather Service · Warnings	
Weblink	https://www.dwd.de/DE/wetter/warnungen_gemeinden/warnWetter_node.html
Content	<p>Slippy map showing areas with apparent weather dangers; clicking on the map opens detailed text warnings for the point specified. Example showing storm warnings over North-Western Germany</p>
Forecast or alert	Pre-alerts and alerts based on short-term weather forecasts
Spatial representation	Warn areas based on German municipalities (approx. 11000 units)
Time representation	Discontinuous updates every few hours, according to the situation.
Data format, volume	Web interface.
Access restrictions	None
Access options	<p>Clicking at a certain location in the map opens a detailed forecast with the warnings relevant for that point. Recent warnings can also be obtained in CAP-Format including geopolygons of the areas affected (Common Alerting Protocol, see https://www.dwd.de/DE/leistungen/opendata/help/warnungen/cap_dwd_profile_en_pdf_2_1_14.pdf), as short messages (SMS) or in form of text forecasts. All of these can be found in subdirectories of https://opendata.dwd.de/weather/alerts/.</p>
Compliance with FAIR	Low. The CAP data are closest to the requirements but lack indexing and machine-readable metadata. Past warnings are regularly deleted without notice.

Germany's Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance (BBK) Warnings	
Weblink	https://warnung.bund.de/meldungen
Content	<p>Web service: a self-updating slippy map with current, clickable official warnings to the population</p>
Forecast or alert	Alerts
Spatial representation	Points or polygons highlighted on the map; district-wise information via RSS feeds. In contrast to the DWD weather warnings, no geodata can be directly obtained.
Time representation	Current, the website updates every 30 seconds.
Data format, volume	Web portal, RSS feeds of negligible volume
Access restrictions	Website only available in German
Access options	The information can also be obtained via a smartphone app called "NINA"; this supports also English and a few other languages. And there are about 400 separate RSS feeds for the administrative districts of Germany.
Compliance with FAIR	Very low. There are neither metadata nor is there any registration of alert messages. Nothing can be downloaded.
Remarks	Denmark lacks such a public overview of civil protection alerts, they rely on a cell broadcast system called "SIRENEN". In Austria, a smartphone app called "KATWARN" is needed to obtain civil protection information in a similar way.

GeoSphere Austria (formerly Zentralanstalt für Meteorologie und Geodynamik, ZAMG) Weather warnings	
Weblink	https://warnungen.zamg.at
Content	<p>Slippy map showing areas with apparent weather dangers; clicking in the highlighted area opens warning details in text form.</p> <p>Example showing a wind warning for most of Austria</p>
Forecast or alert	Warnings based on weather forecasts
Spatial representation	Warn area delineation probably based on municipalities like in Germany, but only aggregated information for the highlighted area is given.
Time representation	Clickable time windows for the next 24 hours, today, tomorrow, the day after tomorrow, and the two following days. Discontinuous updates, according to the situation.
Data format, volume	Web interface.
Access restrictions	None
Access options	The language can be switched to English. In addition, a text message service (SMS) for mobile phones is offered.
Compliance with FAIR	Very low. A corresponding text about warning items and levels may represent the metadata. Indexing, machine-readability and persistence are however completely lacking.
Remarks	

GeoSphere Austria · INCA and other gridded meteorological data products	
Weblink	https://data.hub.geosphere.at/dataset/
Content	<p>High-resolution meteorological fields for Austria integrated from all available sources; variables include temperature, precipitation, wind, global radiation, relative humidity, dew point, and air pressure.</p> <p>Example of a 15-min INCA precipitation analysis based on the combination of rain gauge and radar data (1930 UTC 19 Jun 2009); the bottom-right panel shows the final composite map.</p> <p>Source: Haiden et al. (2021) Weather and Forecasting 26, 2; https://doi.org/10.1175/2010WAF2222451.1</p>
Forecast or alert	Short-term nowcasting for precipitation, temperature, dew point, wind and relative humidity
Spatial representation	1-km grid in Austrian Lambert projection, EPSG:31287
Time representation	Hourly, real-time; archived data start in 2011
Data format, volume	NetCDF, roughly 250 MB per variable and month
Access restrictions	None
Access options	There is also a tool to obtain spatial subsets, and CSV files can be provided for single grid points.
Compliance with FAIR	Medium to High. Although indexing seems to be missing, the data are assigned to unique links. Basic metadata is shown with the download buttons and can be exported to XML, N3 and TTL formats.
Remarks	Until recently, one could hardly get any observational data from ZAMG except the monthly HISTALP data. The publication of the INCA grids is a big step in favour of high-fidelity and real-time hydrological modelling in Austria.

Austria's Federal Ministry for Agriculture, Forestry, Regions, and Water Management (BML) · eHYD	
Weblink	https://ehyd.gov.at
Content	<p>A hydrometrical information system integrating and linking to the data portals of the Austrian federal states' water authorities</p> <p>Image from eHYD's flood situation monitoring page. Gauge symbols link to further information from the responsible state authority.</p>
Forecast or alert	Alert levels shown for gauge stations; forecasts are available from some of the federal states' authorities to which links are provided.
Spatial representation	Time series from point locations
Time representation	Usually daily
Data format, volume	Web portal. Besides map services as shown above, it provides access to sets of cp1252-encoded CSV files in German notation (decimal comma, separator semicolon) for each station containing water level and discharge data. The complete surface water observation history of Austria currently takes about 100 MB of disk space.
Access restrictions	None
Access options	Clickable downloads – there are several options to access different sub-collections of the full data stock.
Compliance with FAIR	Medium. The CSV tables lack indexing. Metadata are fundamentals of observation stations, called »Stammdaten« in German. These share a common text format, the use of FAIR vocabularies is however unsure.
Remarks	Like in Germany, water issues are principally handled by the federal states. Though in contrast to Germany, it is possible to easily and freely access all the country's hydrological data in one spot.

Civil Protection Directorate, Hungarian Ministry of the Interior · Event Map

Weblink	https://www.katasztrofavedelem.hu/modules/vesz/esemenyterkep
Content	<p>Clickable map showing districts with catastrophic events including traffic accidents</p> <p>2023.11.16. 16:44 Személygépkocsi és kisteherautó ütközött a 46-os főúton <i>Közlekedési baleset</i></p> <p>2023.11.16. 16:06 Lesodródott az úttestről egy személygépkocsi a 89-es főúton</p>
Forecast or alert	Alert
Spatial representation	Geopolygons used for the visualization.
Time representation	Current warnings with time stamps
Data format, volume	Web map, clickable text warnings.
Access restrictions	None
Access options	There are no downloadable data.
Compliance with FAIR	Very low. There are neither metadata nor is there any registration of alert messages. Nothing can be downloaded.
Remarks	It remains unclear whether floods and droughts are among the sorts of events displayed here.

Hungarian Meteorological Service (OMSZ) · Weather warnings	
Weblink	https://www.met.hu/en/idojaras/veszelyjelzes/
Content	<p>Weather warnings for Hungarian regions. Regional text information shows on mouseover.</p>
Forecast or alert	Warnings
Spatial representation	Map image based on 179 Hungarian districts (járásog)
Time representation	Updated in irregular intervals (up to several times in a single day).
Data format, volume	Web portal / map images of a few dozen kB each.
Access restrictions	None
Access options	The user can switch to an English language version of the website.
Compliance with FAIR	Very low. There are neither metadata nor is there any registration of warning messages. Nothing can be downloaded, and past warnings are regularly deleted without notice.
Remarks	

Hungarian Hydrological Forecasting Service · Hydroinfo	
Weblink	https://www.hydroinfo.hu
Content	<p>Besides time series graphs (as shown below) and overview maps of water level forecasts, there are more detailed weather observations available than from national weather service's website.</p> <p>Note however that there are no runoff volume data on this site.</p>
Forecast or alert	Forecasts including alert level information
Spatial representation	Data from/for gauge stations of major rivers
Time representation	Daily values in tables, 6-hourly in graphs. Irregular updates.
Data format, volume	Map images, time series graphs and tables. New or updated data may take less than 5 MB per day.
Access restrictions	None
Access options	The tabulated data are embedded in HTML web pages.
Compliance with FAIR	Low. Tabulated data are non-uniformly formatted in HTML, metadata is limited to switchable text windows with quite general information. No indexing takes place.
Remarks	Only the Hungarian language version of the website includes historical daily water level data reaching back into the 1870s.

Hungarian Ministry of the Interior, National Water Directorate General - Water Website	
Weblink	https://www.vizugy.hu/
Content	<p>A website bundling hydrological and water management information from different Hungarian authorities</p> <p>The screenshot shows the website's navigation menu with links like 'Kezdőlap', 'OMIT', 'Folyók, tavak', 'Kvassay Jenő Nemzeti Vízstratégia', 'Vízgyűjtő gazdálkodás', 'Víziközmű', 'Vízügyi fejlesztések', 'Vízügy', 'Térképtár', and 'Médiatár'. Below the menu are tabs for 'Operatív vízállások', 'Árvízvédelmi fokozatok', 'Belvízvédelmi fokozatok', 'Aszály fokozatok', and 'Talajvízszintek'. A main map of Hungary displays numerous blue square markers representing gauging stations. A legend on the right side of the map lists 19 water management regions (vízgyűjtő területe) such as 'Duna vízgyűjtő területe', 'ÉDUVIZIG (Győr)', 'KDUVIZIG (Budapest)', etc., along with a legend for water level status: 'Elrendelő vízmerce', 'Vízmerce', 'Nincs készülttség', 'Vízmerce, I. fokban', 'Vízmerce, II. fokban', 'Vízmerce, III. fokban', and 'Vízmerce, Rendkívüli kész.'.</p>
Forecast or alert	Actual water level alerts at gauging stations. Forecasts can be visualized through links from the main web site.
Spatial representation	Generally gauging station locations.
Time representation	Generally daily, but some near real-time data are sampled more often.
Data format, volume	Different formats including tabulated values in HTML pages and PDF scans from 140 years of hydrological yearbooks.
Access restrictions	Website content only available in Hungarian language
Access options	
Compliance to FAIR	Very low. Most of the FAIR principles seem to be neglected.
Remarks	A not so well-ordered treasure trove of hydro data. I could not find historical runoff data in downloadable format except from the yearbook PDFs, but I might just have missed the correct button.

UNEP Risk Project (formerly UNEP Preview)	
Weblink	https://wesr.unepgrid.ch/?project=MX-XVK-HPH-OGN-HVE-GGN&language=en&theme=color_light
Content	<p>A slippery world map to which numerous natural hazard layers can be selected. Available topics include fires, earthquakes, volcanoes, tsunamis, floods, landslides, tropical cyclones, and multi hazards.</p> <p>The example image shows flood risk potential in the Central Danube area for a 100-year-flood: the deeper the blue the higher the expected inundation. Note however that the effect of levees had generally not been considered for this estimation.</p>
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	Different grid resolutions depending on the different original data sources
Time representation	Different time windows, in a few cases adjustable by a slider.
Data format, volume	Web map portal without any download options
Access restrictions	Not observed; the viewability of single data layers might however be restricted to UN personnel
Access options	Topics and layers can be activated and deactivated by clicking in a menu (outside the sample image)
Compliance with FAIR	Not applicable. This is only a viewer for a selection of original data sources.
Remarks	<p>The layer tabs always contain the original data source of the single layers; if any of the geodata is to be obtained in digital form, these sources are the first addresses to browse.</p> <p>See also https://unepgrid.ch/en/activity/1BDE1705</p>

UNDRR · DesInventar Sendai	
Weblink	https://www.desinventar.net/
Content	<p>Queryable database of disaster records from many (mainly development) countries of the world</p> <p>Example query output: Deaths (left) and record counts (right) by disaster type for the Valparaíso region of Chile</p>
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	Countries and their subdivisions on province and district level
Time representation	Event-based. Country records cover different time slices, e.g., 1933–2020 for Panama or 1980–2010 for Egypt.
Data format, volume	Screen output and Excel or CSV files for download. Volume depends on query.
Access restrictions	None
Access options	Queries can be tailored by up to eight different features (e.g., spatio-temporal boundaries, disaster type or effects). It is also possible to generate simple thematic maps, e.g., of loss intensities. Raw data – shapefiles and an XML database – can be downloaded per country.
Compliance with FAIR	Very Low. Besides textual information, there is hardly any metadata. No indexing takes place.
Remarks	There is hardly any coverage in the DIRECTED RWLs.

EC's Joint Research Centre (JRC) · DRMKC Risk Data Hub	
Weblink	https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/risk-data-hub#/
Content	<p>A “GIS web platform of European wide risk data and methodologies for Disaster Risk Assessment” – Provides the results of multi-hazard assessments for vulnerability, exposure, and risk for European statistical regions. There is also a data base of actual disaster losses since 1960.</p> <p>Example from the Risk Module Map Viewer: River flood risk for buildings in the Emilia Romagna Region, Italy</p>
Forecast or alert	Vulnerability forecasts for the next 10 years
Spatial representation	Countries and their NUTS divisions (all levels)
Time representation	Time-aggregated and annual data, generally since 2005
Data format, volume	All data from the visualizations can be downloaded through a Risk Data Hub API in form of GeoJSON files (default). Other available formats include CSV and Excel. The volume depends on the query.
Access restrictions	No restrictions for online GIS visualizations; obtaining the API key to access the raw data requires registration.
Access options	Too numerous to list them in detail.
Compliance with FAIR	Medium. Disaster and exposure datasets have got PIDs. The web viewer links to data files of the content selected for visualization. There are lots of metadata, however not machine-readable and not always directly linked to the data they describe.
Remarks	Selecting a geographical unit in the Risk Module Map Viewer shows its subdivisions but makes the other units around vanish.

Danube Reference Data and Service Infrastructure (DRDSI)	
Weblink	https://drdsi.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ – not functional any more!
Content	<p>There is still an online description of the former contents available: https://jei.uni-ruse.bg/Issue-2015/12.Paper_DRDSI_Best_Practice_JEI_Final_Checked_web.pdf</p> <p>According to this document, a total of 6712 datasets had been registered on the DRDSI platform as of 25 January 2016. More than half linked to geodatasets from national INSPIRE services. The other items were metadata about data resources identified by stakeholders, other data portals, projects, and institutions.</p>
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	Geodata according to the INSPIRE standards
Time representation	Geodata according to the INSPIRE standards
Data format, volume	Geodata could be visualized and eventually downloaded through the Web frontend which also displayed the metadata.
Access restrictions	None
Access options	
Compliance with FAIR	Not applicable. DRDSI was a meta-collection of original data sources.
Remarks	The JRC server behind the internet link rejects connections since 2021 or even earlier. As the infrastructure had been set up by a project that ended in 2016, it can be assumed that follow-up maintenance was not intended to last forever.

Centre for Research on the Epidemiology of Disasters (CRED) EM-DAT – The International Disaster Database	
Weblink	https://www.emdat.be/ , https://public.emdat.be/
Content	<p>A database of currently more than 26,000 disaster records, about 2/3 of them natural disasters. It can be queried similar to Des-Inventar Sendai and the catalog of the DRMKC Risk Data Hub.</p> <p>Example of a query being prepared.</p>
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	Search granularity are countries. Disaster areas are located by geographical names; there are fields for geographical coordinates, but these are quite often without entry.
Time representation	Start and end day of the event. The database starts by the year 1900, but event coverage before 2000 is rather incomplete.
Data format, volume	Database query via web interface, output in form of Excel sheets. Conversion to graphical output (maps, graphs) is not included.
Access restrictions	Registration required
Access options	The query mask allows for subsetting by two hierarchical selections: the type of event (e.g., hydrological with floods and flash floods as sub-categories) and the geographical region (by continents, sub-continents, and countries). In addition, a period of years can be selected.
Compliance with FAIR	Very low. No data seems to be registered, and there are no metadata beyond the user manual. The provenance of single entries is unclear – why is the location of a fire in the Black Forest, a landscape in Germany, given in French (Forêt Noire)?
Remarks	EM-DAT does not only contain natural but also man-made (technical) disasters, but the coverage is incomplete; e.g., the collapse of Cologne's city archive in 2009 is missing. EM-DAT was established in 1988 by a cooperation of CRED (UCLouvain) and the World Health Organization (WHO). The main sponsor is USAID.

Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA) IdroGEO – The Italian platform on hydrogeological instability	
Weblink	https://idrogeo.isprambiente.it/app/
Content	<p>IdroGeo is a “modular information system that allows the management and consultation of data, maps, reports, photos, videos, and documents of the Italian Landslide Inventory (IFFI), national hazard maps, and landslide and flood risk indicators.” This was stated by Iadanza et al. (2021), https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi10020089, a publication presenting IdroGeo in detail.</p>
Forecast or alert	No
Spatial representation	Administrative levels Italy–Macroregions–Regions–Provinces–Municipalities and smaller sub-areas for mapping
Time representation	Current, updates when new data become available.
Data format, volume	Web map application with download options for CSV and Excel data tables plus metadata in Excel format. In addition, there are direct downloads for open data (e.g., shapefiles).
Access restrictions	None
Access options	There is a hazard–risk view and the Italian landslide inventory.
Compliance to FAIR	Low. None of the data is registered or indexed, and some datasets lack external metadata (e.g., the geodata). Proprietary formats (MS Excel, ESRI Shapefile) are favoured.
Remarks	A well-curated tool illustrating the regional and local risk situation in an easily accessible and understandable yet detail-rich presentation

Partners

